

**“A STUDY ON EFFECTIVNESS OF LEGAL
COMPLIANCE FOR EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT”**

**[A STUDY ON 60 EMPLOYEES OF GODREJ
INDUSTRIES LTD. VALIA. BHARUCH]**

A RESEARCH DISSERTATION

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RESEARCH GUIDE

RESEARCHER

MR.MOIN MALEK

RIFAKAT S. SAIYAD

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PREFACE

As we all know that “Practice makes a man perfect” & perfection in technical study is the backbone of all industrial working. Every coin has two sides; similarly knowledge has two faces, theoretical & practical. Without theory we can’t understand practical & without practical knowledge, theoretical knowledge is like a ship without radar.

In Industrial Law training we get a chance to observe industrial atmosphere, various industrial problems like industrial dispute, wages, fatal accident, child labour & Provident funds done by chance etc. We can’t have experience of all these while sitting in class rooms.

Although it doesn’t give 100% practical knowledge but this is helpful for evoking curiosity & interest for actual industrial world. In short it is like bringing a frog from a well to sea shore & let him see that how looks like the real water.

Here is presented a dissertation on topic “a study on effectiveness of Legal Compliance for employee development”

Acknowledgement

"I think leadership comes from integrity - which you do whatever you ask others to do. I think there are non-obvious ways to lead. Just by providing a good example as a parent, a friend, a neighbor makes it possible for other people to see better ways to do things. Leadership does not need to be a dramatic, fist in the air and trumpets blaring, activity."

I am sincerely thankful to **Mr. Rajendra Mithaiwala, [P&A Manager]**, **Mr. Viraf Kelawala and Mrs. Kailash Patel [HR officers]** at Godrej Industries LTD, Bharuch for granting me permission to collect information as well as helping me a clear rapport with the respondents and support me to familiar with all department and employees of GIL.

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INDEX

SR. NO.	TOPIC	PAGE NO.
*	PREFACE	---
*	ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	---
*	CONTENTS	---
*	LIST OF TABLE	---
I	INTRODUCTION & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	1
II	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	
III	RESEARCH SETTING	
IV	DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION	
V	FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS & SUGGESTIONS	
*	ANNEXURE	
A	BIBLIOGRAPHY	---
B	INTERVIEW SCHEDULE	---

SR.NO.	TABLE	PAGE NO
1	Table showing age of the respondents	
2	Table showing Designation of the respondents	
3	Table showing Department of the respondents	
4	Table showing Grade of the respondents	
5	Table showing awareness of the respondents regarding legal compliances	
6	Table showing safety equipment provided by company to the respondents.	
7	Table showing equipment for safety provided to the respondents	
8	Table showing awareness of minimum wages	
9	Table showing nomination form under social security's Acts	
10	Table showing mobile allow to only officer in the company	
11	Table Showing industrial law seminar conducted by company	
12	Table showing satisfaction of boiler plant security	
13	Table showing license for deployed labour contractor	
14	Table showing weekly off payment to worker	
15	Table showing duration of rest interval	
16	Table showing locker provided by company to respondents	
17	Table showing extra facilities provided to night shift worker	
18	Table showing satisfaction of welfare facilities	

19	Table showing quality of food in canteen	
20	Table showing satisfaction for transportation as a safe and adequate.	
21	Table showing satisfaction of medical facility	
22	Table showing legal compliance will help employee to get proper facilities.	
23	Table showing development of organizational environment.	
24	Table showing existing condition of legal compliances	
25	Table showing improvement of quality of life through legal compliances.	
26	Table showing socio-economic development through legal compliances	
27	Table showing needs of more effectiveness of legal compliances	
28	Table showing skill development of employee through apprenticeship.	
29	Table showing cleanliness in company for better health	
30	Table showing satisfaction of respondents for loan facility.	
31	Table showing protection of human rights	
32	Tables showing necessity of legal compliances	
33	Table showing training regarding legal compliance	
34	Table showing means of awareness of legal compliance	
35	Table showing support for problems regarding legal compliance.	

36	Table showing enhancement of performance of organization through legal compliance	
37	Table showing respondents' opinion for welfare facility and its effect of work	

CHAPTER-I

INTRODUCTION

The development and establishment of a legal compliance system is one of the most important tasks for an organization in order to secure the soundness and appropriateness of its employee. Therefore, the institution's management is charged with and responsible for taking the initiative in developing and establishing the legal compliance system that covers the organization's entire development by deciding a basic policy on legal compliance and developing an organizational framework, etc..

The prime function of legal compliances is to development of policy and it has some Roles and Responsibilities that is to improve the legal compliance based on a full recognition that full legal Compliance throughout the financial institution is vital for maintaining public confidence in the institution and securing the soundness and appropriateness of the organization's development.

Through our history we know that employee or the labor suffer a lot with the capitalist system but with a strong impact of constitutional power condition of employee developed well and this drastic change was just because of this legal compliances and it has very good influence on employee development. We are rich enough in constitutional provisions which play a major role in employee development and make their life more stable and happy.

IMPORTANCE OF LEGAL COMPLIANCE:-

Implementation of Compliance Program

The Compliance Control Division implement specific measures of the Compliance Program in a timely and appropriate manner conduct

follow-up verification of the status of progress and achievement and report it to the Board of Directors or equivalent organization to the Board of Directors.

Communication and Collection of Information

From the viewpoint of ensuring the full enforcement of legal compliance throughout the institution, the Compliance Control Division collect, manage, analyze and examine in an integrated manner Compliance-related Information scattered across the institution's divisions and departments and, based on the results of the analysis and examination, take appropriate steps and measures. In particular, the divisions collect information in close coordination with persons in charge of compliance allocated to operation divisions and sales branches, etc

Monitoring of Legal Compliance

The Compliance Control Division monitor the status of legal compliance at operation divisions and sales branches, etc. on an ongoing basis in order to ensure full legal compliance throughout the institution.

For example, the division conduct monitoring by requiring reports in a regular and timely manner or on an as needed basis from persons in charge of compliance with regard to the status of legal compliance at operation divisions and sales branches, etc., or by collecting information on an ongoing basis and conducting a field survey in a timely manner.

Coordination with Customer Support Manager

The Compliance Control Division appropriately maintains coordination with the Customer Support Manager as required under

the Customer Protection Management System and provides advice to help facilitate customer support.

The Compliance Control Division collect information in a prompt and wide-ranging Manner with regard to requests for consultations and complaints from customers⁹ that should be recognized as legitimate complaints or that are likely to develop into legitimate complaints.

With regard to requests for consultations and complaints that involve information concerning violation of Laws, does the Compliance Control Division require and obtain reports from divisions, departments and individuals that hold the relevant information in an appropriate manner analyze and examine the information and provide feedback to the division in charge of processing complaints?

The Compliance Control Division have non-interested parties conduct appropriate and ⁹ See Checklist for Customer Protection Management. Sufficient investigations to identify the cause with regard to requests for consultations and Complaints determined as requiring such action.

Roles of Persons in Charge of Compliance

Persons in charge of compliance keep under unified control Compliance-related information at the divisions and departments to which they are allocated, communicate the information to the Compliance Control Division in a regular and timely manner or on an as needed basis and appropriately engage in efforts to ensure compliance at the divisions and departments. They perform their functions fully based on the legal knowledge accumulated with regard to their operations.

Need of legal compliance

Legal compliance is the process or procedure to ensure that an organization follows relevant laws, regulations and business rules. The definition of legal compliance, especially in the context of corporate legal departments, has recently been expanded to include understanding and adhering to ethical codes within entire professions, as well. There are two requirements for an enterprise to be compliant with the law, first its policies need to be consistent with the law. Second, its policies need to be complete with respect to the law. The role of legal compliance has also been expanded to include self-monitoring the non-governed behavior with industries and corporations that could lead to workplace indiscretions Within the LGRC realm, it is important to keep in mind that if a strong legal governance component is in place, risk cannot be accurately assessed, nor can the monitoring of legal compliance be carried out efficiently. It is also important to realize that within the LGRC framework, legal teams work closely with executive teams and other business departments to align their goals and ensure proper communication.

Legal Consistency

Legal Consistency is property that declares enterprise policies to be free of contradictions with the law. **Legal Consistency** has been defined as not having multiple verdicts for the same case. The antonym **Legal Inconsistency** is defined as having two rules that contradict each other common definitions of consistency refer to “treating similar cases alike”. In the enterprise context, legal consistency refers to “obedience to the law”. In the context of legal requirements validation, legal consistency is defined as, “Enterprise requirements are legally consistent if they adhere to the legal requirements and include no contradictions.”

Legal Completeness

Legal Completeness is a property that declares enterprise policies to cover all scenarios included or suggested by the law. Completeness suggests that there are no scenarios covered by the law that cannot be implemented in the enterprise. In addition, it implies that all scenarios not allowed by the law are not allowed by the enterprise.

Enterprise policies are said to be legally complete if they contain no gaps in the legal sense. Completeness can be thought of in two ways: Some scholars make use of a concept of 'obligation' completeness such as Ayres and Gartner. According to this usage, a system or a contract is 'obligation ally' complete if it specifies what each party is to do in every situation, even if this is not the optimal action to take under some circumstances. Others discuss 'enforceability' completeness in the sense that failing to specify key terms can lead a court to characterize a system as being too uncertain to enforce (*May & Butcher v the King* 1934), and hence a system may be complete with respect to enforceability. This leads to the following definition: enterprise regulations or requirements are legally complete if it specifies what each party is to do in each situation while covering all gaps in the legal sense..

Principles of legal compliance

Traditionally, corporations which complied with the dictates of applicable legislation would have regarded not just their legal, but also their social obligations, as ending at that point. Socio-legal research suggested that corporations complied with law only for instrumental reasons (to avoid legal penalties) (Hawkins & Hutter, 1993) or because, "regulations are taken to be a measure of societal expectations, and thus interpreted as a guide to an organization's moral and social duties (Wright, 1998). From this traditional point of view, corporations could be expected to take actions which went

“beyond compliance” only where they saw some self-interest in doing so, such as increasing profit, usually over the short term (Porter & Van der Linde?).¹ Today, however, at least in economically advanced democracies, many corporations no longer perceive their social obligations as necessarily synonymous with their legal obligations. Two decades of tightening regulatory rules and legal threats have led many businesspeople to assume that any hazards and harms that their enterprise engenders, even if not clearly illegal today, will sooner or later be subject to public censure,

The Principles of Legal Compliance are:

1. Commitment
2. Ownership
3. Demonstrable (Transparency)
4. Comprehensive
5. Systematic
6. Ongoing Development

To find out what each principle represents and encompasses refer below:

1. Commitment: There must be a commitment to an effective legal compliance process by local elected members, management and staff. The local authority's commitment to compliance should be publicly recorded in a clear and unequivocal manner. The commitment to legal compliance should be manifested in approved policies and in the accountability demanded from the Chief Executive. The commitment to legal compliance should be part of the culture of the local authority.

2. Ownership: Legal compliance, and the processes which underpin it, are to be owned by all persons within the local authority. While there will be varying roles and responsibilities for different people within the local authority, it is important that the elected members,

Chief Executive and all staff have a clear understanding and ownership of the objectives and process of legal compliance. The ownership by elected members will be manifested through policy statements on legal compliance and ensuring the Chief Executive has compliance systems in place. The ownership of the Chief Executive will be recognized by taking primary responsibility to ensure that local authority's commitment is realized. This is usually brought about through the development and implementation of formal compliance systems. All staff of the local authority should be encouraged, through formal and informal means, to recognize the importance of legal compliance in their daily work and to, collectively and individually, contribute to a culture of compliance.

3. Demonstrable (Transparency): Local Authorities are public bodies. Their legal compliance framework and processes should be developed in an open transparent manner, be available to the public, with periodic reporting to the public on legal compliance processes and outcomes. The legal compliance framework and process should be open to public scrutiny. While the framework and processes may be developed by staff and management, they should be submitted to, and discussed in an open Council meeting before adoption. As part of the local authority's accountability to its stakeholders, two forms of reporting are necessary to demonstrate the legal compliance process is working as intended. The first accountability is from management to the local authority, and the second accountability is from the local authority to the general public. The accountability of the local authority to the public regarding legal compliance could be incorporated as part of a statement of governance and risk management in the annual report. Internationally, such statements are an increasingly important component of Boards of Directors annual reporting to shareholders. It is likely that the bulk of the legal

compliance procedures and programmes which underpin the framework will remain in-house, as they are technical and procedural documents which are unlikely to be of interest to the public.

4. Comprehensive: The local authority's legal compliance processes should embrace legislation and case law as well as a clearly defined ambit of other standards, codes of practice or other authoritative pronouncements.

The legal compliance process must embrace:

- Acts of Parliaments, including Public Acts; and Local and Private Acts which apply to local authority all statutory regulations;
- Case law;
- Local authority by-laws;
- Regional and District Plans;
- The extent to which other authoritative pronouncements are included in the legal compliance process is a decision for each local authority to make. However local authorities must clearly define the types of authoritative pronouncements which will form part of their legal compliance;
- Authoritative pronouncements which could form part of legal compliance include:
 - Standards issued by Standards NZ codes of practice issued by reputable national or representative bodies Charters or customer agreements.

5. Systematic: There must be a systematic approach to support and sustain legal compliance activities. The systematic approach should be embedded into existing management systems. Whenever possible legal compliance systems and processes should be embedded within management systems within local authority. Legal compliance systems are a fundamental part of good management and therefore

should not be seen as a "bolt on" task unrelated to normal business. Legal compliance systems should also form part of the local authority's integrated risk management processes. The NZ handbook of Risk Management for Local Government (SNZ 4360: 2000) includes legal compliance as one of the seven core risk management activities of local government. To support and sustain legal compliance there must be formal systems put in place which cover training, written procedures (programmes), action plans, complaints handling, assignment of roles, monitoring, reporting and record-keeping. Each of the elements of the systematic approach is further elaborated below.

- **Training:** Relevant staff to acquire knowledge of legal environment relevant to their activities, and their part in the legal compliance process.
- **Compliance Programmes:** Covering the full range of local authority activities; Written in plain language; Tailored to functions; customized to suit the circumstances of relevant staff; Updated regularly; Capable of providing certification or assurance that "builds" upwards within the organization.
- **Action Plans:** Provide a springboard for subsequent action, treatment or remedies; provide guidance for amending or streamlining future compliance programmes.
- **Complaints Handling:** Procedures for handling complaints from staff, ratepayers, service users, or community groups
- **Roles and Responsibilities:** Appointment of a legal compliance co coordinator; Inclusion of legal compliance responsibilities in job descriptions; Roles of local authority external legal advisors and insurance agents
- **Monitoring:** Regular, in-house quality assurance procedures; Review of completed compliance programmes; Classifying and investigating compliance failures.

- **Reporting:** Tiered reporting structure that reports more important issues to local authority and management; Regular confirmation that compliance systems are being maintained; regular reporting on effectiveness of procedures and instances of non compliance.
- **Record Keeping:** Nature and type of records to be kept; Confidentiality / security of sensitive material; Availability for insurers and legal advisers.

6. Ongoing Development - A programme of continuous improvement will ensure that the objectives of legal compliance remain relevant, and its effectiveness will be heightened. Legal Compliance will only be effective if it is kept relevant and fresh, with continuous attention to address newly emerging issues as well as streamlining existing compliance processes. Development through staff training is an important element. This should include:

- Legal compliance as part of induction programmes for new staff;
- Staff attending internal or external workshops on specific areas of law or application of the law;
- Briefing by local authority's legal advisers;
- Networking with other local authorities.

Legal compliance training should be integrated with the local authority's professional development programmes for each member of staff. The legal compliance process will be enhanced if the local authority has ongoing liaison with its legal advisers, insurers, and risk consultants and regulators.

The aim will be to anticipate and manage issues while they are still on the horizon. Such liaison should be regular and proactive, particularly with insurers and legal advisers. Where possible local authority should also seek to comment on draft legislation or codes of practice, not only from the standpoint of the efficacy of the legislation, but also from the compliance perspective. In addition to the regular

in-house quality assurance as part of the systematic approach to legal compliance, periodic external assessment should be conducted of local authority's approach to legal compliance.

The aim of the reviews is to see that the objectives of the legal compliance approach are being met, that designed procedures in place are adequate to meet the objectives, and that the designed procedures are happening and not becoming stale. An important aspect of ongoing development is to ensure that administrative procedures improve as a result of the legal compliance programmes. If there are issues emerging, identifying how these can be translated into different ways of working.

Compliance Strategy

Effectively managing the compliance function maximizes opportunities in the market and enhances the Bank's competitive position by building trust. Integrating a strong compliance function into the daily management of business and strategic planning gives the organization a competitive advantage. It helps the Bank to protect its reputation, lower cost of capital, reduce costs and minimize the risk of investigation, prosecution and penalties because things are being done the right way.

Mission of the Compliance Function

- To build together with the Bank's Business and Support units, a sustainable competitive advantage
- By fully integrating compliance management in daily business activities and strategic planning.

Main Purposes of the Compliance Function

The main purposes of the Compliance Function are:

Understanding

Understanding and advocating the rules, regulations and laws and the effective management of the compliance function by proactively working with and advising business/support units to manage the compliance function throughout the Bank's products and service life cycle to meet stakeholder expectations.

Reporting/Controlling

Developing and Enhancing Tools to strengthen the three lines of defense to detect, communicate, report and manage the compliance function and compliance issues in order to limit surprises.

Strategic Direction

Supporting BOV's Strategy by establishing clear roles and responsibilities to help embed good compliance practice throughout the business

Disclosure

Deepening the Culture of Compliance by partnering with the business to increase the culture of trust, accountability, transparency and integrity in evaluating and managing the compliance function

Definition and Scope of the Compliance Function

The Compliance Function

The compliance function reduces the risk of impairment of BOV's integrity. A failure (or perceived failure) to comply with the Bank's business principles and the compliance-related laws/obligations, regulations, codes of conduct and standards that are relevant to the specific financial and investment services offered by a business or its

ensuing activities, could damage BOV's reputation, lead to legal or regulatory sanctions and/or financial loss.

Integrity and Reputation

Integrity is the focus in managing a compliance obligation. However, reputation is also one possible second order effect of a compliance breach, in addition to (direct) financial loss, as it includes loss of new or future business, existing clients and/or trust in BOV's integrity.

3.3 Four Conduct Related Integrity Areas

The Table below highlights the main Conduct Related Integrity Areas monitored by the Compliance

Function.

1. Customer Conduct Related Integrity Area
 2. BOV Officer Conduct Related Integrity Area
 3. Investment Services Conduct Related Integrity Area
 4. Organizational Conduct Related Integrity Area
- Money Laundering Market abuse and personal trading Marketing, sales and trading conduct related integrity area.
 - Organizational conflicts of interest, market abuse and insider trading conduct related integrity area.
 - Terrorist Financing Breaches of the BOV business principles, Special License Conditions or Code of Conduct of advisory and discretionary management business.
 - Consumer Protection laws Political or reputational exposed person.
 - Transparency of product offerings (e.g. costs, disclosures, T&Cs etc) New or modified products and services (e.g. customer base, design) and governance changes.
 - Customer engagements or transactions with sanctioned countries Gifts or entertainment given or received; bribery Complaint handling Agreed sector/industry standards.

- External incident reporting.
- Data protection/Professional secrecy Regulatory registration/licensing and reporting requirements.

TYPES OF LEGAL AND STATUTORY COMPLIANCE

- Apprentices Act, 1961
- Child Labour (Prohibition & Regulation) Act, 1986
- Contract Labour (Regulation & Abolition) Act, 1970
- Employee's Provident Funds & Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952 & The Schemes.
- Employment Exchange (Compulsory Notification of Vacancies) Act, 1959 & the Rule.
- Industrial Employment (Standing Orders) Act, 1946
- Boilers Act, 1923 (Indian)
- Equal Remuneration Act, 1976
- Maternity Benefit Act, 1961
- Factory Act, 1948
- Minimum Wages Act, 1948
- Payment of Bonus Act, 1965
- Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972
- Payment of Wages Act, 1936
- Workmen's Compensation Act 1923

**DETAILED ABOUT TYPES OF LEGAL AND STATUTORY
COMPLIANCE**

Apprentices Act, 1961

Object of the Act

Promotion of new manpower at skills. Improvement/refinement of old skills through theoretical and practical training in number of trades and occupation.

Applicability of the Act (Sec. 1)

Areas and industries as notified by the Central Government.

Apprenticeship Advisor (Sec.2 (b))

Central Apprenticeship Advisor – when appointed by Central Government.

Industry [Sec.2 (k)]

Industry means any industry or business or in which any trade, occupation or subject/field in engineering or technology or any vocational course may be specified as a designated trade.

Qualification for being trained as an Apprentice (Sec.3)

A person cannot be an apprentice in any designated trade unless

- He is not more than 14 years of age;
- He satisfies such standard of education and physical fitness as May be prescribed.

Contract of Apprenticeship (Sec.4)

To contain such terms and conditions as may be agreed to by the apprentice, or his guardian (in case he is a minor) and employers.

Conditions for Notation of Contract of Apprenticeship (Sec.5)

- There exists an apprenticeship contract.
- The employer is unable to fulfill his obligation.
- The approval of the Apprenticeship Advisor is obtained.
- Agreement must be registered with the Apprenticeship Advisor.

Period of Apprenticeship

Training to be determined by the National Council.

Termination of Apprenticeship (Sec.6)

On the expiry of the period of Apprenticeship training. On the application by either of the parties to the contract to the Apprenticeship Advisor.

Payment to Apprentices (Sec.6)

The employer to pay such stipend at a rate of not less than the prescribed minimum rate as may be specified.

Number of Apprentices in Designated Trade (Sec.8)

To be determined by The Central Government after consulting the Central Apprenticeship Council.

Period of Apprenticeship

Training to be determined by the National Council.

Obligations of Employers (Sec.11)

- To provide the apprentice with the training in his trade.
- To ensure that a person duly qualified is placed in charge of the training of the apprentice.
- To carry out contractual obligations.

Obligations of Apprentice (Sec.12)

- To learn his trade conscientiously, diligently.
- To attend practical and instructional classes regularly.
- To carry out all lawful orders.
- To carry out his contractual obligations.

Health safety & Welfare measures for Apprentices (Sec.14)

As per Factories Act or Mines Act as the case may be when undergoing training.

Hours of work (Sec.15)

- 42 to 48 in a week while on theoretical training.
- 42 in a week while on basic training.
- 42 to 45 in a week in second year of training.
- As per other workers (in the third year).
- Not allowed to work between 10 PM to 4 AM unless approved by Apprenticeship Advisor.

Leave and Holidays

- Casual leave for the maximum period of 12 days in a year.
- Medical leave for the maximum period of 15 days and the accumulated leave upto 40 days in a year.
- Extraordinary leave upto a maximum period of 10 days in a year.

Employer's liability to pay compensation for injury (Sec.16)

As per provisions of Workmen's Compensation Act

Offences & Punishment (Sec. 30 & 31)

Imprisonment of a term up to 6 months or with fine when employer:-

- Engages as an apprentice a person who is not qualified for being so engaged.
- Fails to carry out the terms and conditions of a contract of apprenticeship.
- Contravenes the provisions of the Act relating to the number of apprentices which he is required to engage under those provisions

Apprentices Act 1961 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr. No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 4	Proper Engagement of Apprentice	Contract of Apprenticeship and Registration by Employer	The Employer has properly registered the Agreements of Apprenticeship.
2	Section 19	Record of Apprenticeship	As Notified	Records of Apprenticeship are properly maintained.
3	Rule 14	Return in Form Apprentice-IV	Half Yearly	Filed properly.
		Index Card in Form Apprentice-I	Within 15 days of Employment	Filed properly.
		Record o of Basic/Practical Training Form App 4	Half Yearly	Filed properly.
		Report in Form Apprentice-2	Half Yearly	Filed properly

		Eligibility Particulars in Form Apprentice-3	Nov/May	Filed properly
		Register of Attendance	Monthly	Filed properly
		Index Card in Form Apprentice-5	On Engagement	Filed properly

Child labour (Prohibition & Regulation) Act, 1986

Applicability of the Act

An Act to prohibit the engagement of children in certain Employments and to regulate the conditions of work of children in certain other employments

Definitions

“Approximate Government” means, in relation to an establishment under the control of the central government or a railway administration or a major port or a mine or oilfield, the Central Government, and in all other cases, the state Government.

“Child” means a Person who has not completed his fourteenth year of age.

“Day” means a period means of twenty-four hours beginning at midnight.

“Establishment” includes a shop, commercial establishment, workshop, farm, residential hotel, restaurant, eating house, theatre or other place of public amusement or entertainment.

Prohibition of employment of children in certain occupations and processes

(Sec-3)

No child shall be employed or permitted to work in any of the occupations set forth in Part A of the Schedule or in any workshop wherein any of the processes set forth in Part B of the Schedule is carried on:

Provided that nothing in this section shall apply to any workshop wherein any process is carried on by the occupier with the aid of his family or to any school established by, or receiving assistance or recognition from, Government.

Application of Part (Sec-6)

The provisions of this Part shall apply to an establishment or a class of establishment in which none of the occupations or processes referred to in Section 3 is carried on.

Hours and period of work (Sec-7)

- No child shall be required or permitted to work in any establishment in excess of such number of hours as may be prescribed for such establishment or class of establishments.
- The period of work on each day shall be so fixed that no period shall exceed three hours and that no child shall work for more than three hours before he has had an interval for at least one hour.
- The period of work of a child shall be so arranged that includes of his interval for rest, under sub-section (2), it shall not be spread over more than six hours, including the time spent in waiting for work on any day.
- No child shall be permitted or required to work between 7 p.m and 8 a.m.
- No child shall be required or permitted to work overtime.
- No child shall be required or permitted to work in any establishment on any day on which he has already been working in another establishment.

Weekly holidays (Sec-8)

Every child employed in an establishment shall be allowed in each week, a holiday of one whole day, which day shall be specified by

the occupier in a notice permanently exhibited in a conspicuous place in the establishment and the day so specified shall not be altered by the occupier more than once in three months.

Notice to Inspector (Sec-9)

- Every occupier in relation to an establishment in which a child was employed or permitted to work immediately before the date of commencement of this Act in relation to such establishment shall, with in a period of thirty days from such commencement, send to the Inspector with in whose local limits the establishment is situated, a written notice containing the following particulars, namely:-
 - The name and situation of the establishment.
 - The name of the person in actual management of the establishment.
 - The address to which communication relating to the establishment should be sent.
 - The nature of the occupation or process carried on in the establishment.
- Every occupier, in relation to an establishment, who employs, or permits to work, any child after the date of commencement of this Act in relation to such establishment, shall, with in a period of 30 days from the date of such employment, send to the Inspector within whose local limit the establishment is situated, a written notice containing the particulars as are mentioned in sub-section (1).

Disputes as to age (Sec-10)

If any question arises between an Inspector and an occupier as to the age of any child who is employed or is permitted to work by him in an

establishment, the question shall, in the absence of a certificate as to the age of such child granted by the prescribed medical authority, be referred by the Inspector for decision to the prescribed medical authority.

Maintenance of register (Sec-11)

There shall be maintained by every occupier in respect of children employed or permitted to work in any establishment, a register to be available for inspection by an Inspector at all times during working hours or when work is being carried on in any such establishment, showing-

- The name and date of birth of every child so employed or permitted to work.
- Hours and periods of work of any such child and the intervals of rest to which he is entitled.
- The nature of work of any such child.
- Such other particulars as may be prescribed.

Display of notice containing abstract of Sections 3 & 14 (Sec-12)

Every railway administration, every port authority and every occupier shall cause to be displayed in a conspicuous and accessible place at every station on its railway or within the limits of a port or at the place of work, as the case may be, a notice in the local language and in the English language containing an abstract of Sections 3 and 14.

Health and Safety (Sec-13)

- Cleanliness in the place of work and its freedom from nuisance.
- Disposal of wastes and effluents.
- Ventilation and temperature.

- Dust and fume.
- Lighting, artificial humidification and drinking water.
- Latrine and urinals
- Spittoons, fencing of machinery.
- Floor, stairs and means of access.

Penalties (Sec-14)

- Whoever employs any child or permits any child to work in contravention of the provisions of Section 3 shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which shall not be less than 3 months but which may extend to one years or with fine which shall not be less than ten thousand rupees but which may extend to 20,000 rupees or with both.
- Whoever, having been convicted of an offence under Section 3, commits a like offence afterwards, he shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which shall not be less than six months but which may extend to two years.

Modified application of certain laws in relation to penalties (Sec-15)

Where any person is found guilty and convicted of contravention of any of the provisions mentioned in sub-section(2), he shall be liable to penalties as provided in sub-sections (1) and (2) of section 14 of this Act and not under the Acts in which those provision are contained.

Procedure relating to offences (Sec-16)

- Any person, police officer or Inspector may file a complaint of the commission of an offence under this Act in any court of competent jurisdiction.

- Every certificate as to the age of a child which has been granted by a prescribed medical authority shall, for the purpose of this Act, be conclusive evidence as to the age of the child to whom it relates.
- No court inferior to that of a Metropolitan Magistrate or a Magistrate of the first class shall try any offence under this Act.

Amendment of Act 11 of 1948(Sec-23)

In Section 2 of the Minimum Wages Act, 1948-

For clause (a), the following clauses shall be *substituted*, namely:-

‘Adolescent’ means a person who has completed his 14 year of age but has not completed his 18 year.

‘Adult’ means a person who has completed his 18 year of age.

After clause (b), the following clause shall be *inserted*, namely,

‘Child’ means a person who has not completed his 14 year of age.

Amendment of Act 69 of 1951(Sec-24)

In the Plantations Labour Act, 1951-

- In Section 2, in clause (a) and (c), for the word “fifteenth”, the word “fourteenth” shall be substituted.
- Section 24 shall be omitted.

- In Section 26, in the opening portion, the words “who has completed his 12 year” shall be omitted.

Amendment of Act 44 of 1958(Sec-25)

In the Merchant Shipping Act, 1958, in section 109, for the word “fifteen”, the word “fourteen” shall be substituted.

Amendment of Act 27 of 1961(Sec-26)

In the Motor Transport Workers Act, 1961, in section 2, in clauses (a) and (c) for the word “fifteen”, the word “fourteenth” shall be substituted.

Child Labour (Prohibition & Regulation) Act, 1986 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.N o	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 9	Notice to Inspector	30 days from Estab.	Not Applicable.
2	Section 11/Rule 16	Register of Child Workers in Form A	Continuous	Not Applicable.
3	Section 14	Display of Notice	Continuous	Not Applicable.

Contract Labour (Regulation & Abolition) Act, 1970

Object of the Act

To regulate the employment of contract labor in certain establishments and to provide for its abolition in certain circumstances and for matters connected therewith.

Applicability (Sec - 1)

- Every establishment in which 20 or more workmen are employed or were employed on any day of the preceding 12 months as contract labor.
- Every contractor who employs or who employed on any day of the preceding twelve months 20 or more workmen.

Registration of Establishment (Sec - 7)

Principal employer employing 20 or more workers through the contractor or the contractor(s) on deposit of required fee in Form 1.

Prohibition of Employment of Contract Labour (Sec - 10)

Only by the appropriate Government through issue of notification after consultation with the Board (and not Courts) can order the prohibition of employment of contract labor.

Revocation of Registration (Sec - 9)

When obtained by Misrepresentation or suppression of material facts etc. after opportunity to the principal Employer.

Licensing of Contractor (Sec.12, Rule 21)

- Engaging 10 or more than 20 workers and on deposit of required fee in Form IV.
- Valid for specified period. Sec.12, Rule 21.

Revocation or Suspension & Amendment of Licenses (Sec 14)

- When obtained by misrepresentation or suppression of material facts.
- Failure of the contractor to comply with the conditions or contravention of Act or the Rules.

Welfare measures to be taken by the Contractor (Sec. 16 &17)

Contract labor either one hundred or more employed by a contractor for one or more canteens shall be provided and maintained.

First Aid facilities.

Number of rest-rooms as required under the Act.

Drinking water, latrines and washing facilities. Sec. 16 & 17.

Laws, Agreement or standing orders inconsistent with the Act-Not Permissible - (Sec 20)

Unless the privileges in the contract between the parties or more favorable than the prescribed in the Act, such contract will be invalid and the workers will continue to get more favorable benefits.

Liability of Principal Employer (Sec -20)

To ensure provision for canteen, restrooms, sufficient supply of drinking water, latrines and urinals, washing facilities.

Principal employer entitled to recover from the contractor for providing such amenities or to make deductions from amount payable.

Registers of Contractors (Rule 74, 75, 76 and 77)

Principal employer

To maintain a register of contractor in respect of every establishment in Form XII

Contractor

To maintain register of workers for each registered establishment in Form XIII.

To issue an employment card to each worker in Form XIV.

To issue service certificate to every workman on his termination in Form XV.

Muster Roll, Wages Register, Deduction Register and Overtime

Register by Contractor (Rule – 79, 80 & 81)

Every contractor shall

- Maintain Muster Roll and a Register of Wages in Form XVI and Form XVII respectively when combined.
- Register or wage-cum-Muster Roll in Form XVII where the wage period is a fortnight or less.
- Maintain a Register of Deductions for damage or loss, Register or Fines and Register of Advances in Form XX, from XXI and Form XXII respectively.
- Maintain a Register of Overtime in Form XXIII.
- To issue wage slips in Form XIX, to the workmen at least a day prior to the disbursement of wages.
- Obtain the signature or thumb impression of the worker concerned against the entries relating to him on the Register of wages or Muster Roll-Cum-Wages Register.
- When covered by Payment of Wages Act, register and records to be maintained under the rules
- Muster Roll, Register of wages, Register of Deductions, Register of Overtime, Register of Fines, Register of Advances, Wage slip

- To display an abstract of the act and Rules in English and Hindi and in the language spoken by the Majority of workers in such forms as may be approved by appropriate authority.
- To display notices showing rates of wages, hours of work, wage period, dates of payment, names and addresses of the inspector and to send copy to the inspector and any change for with.

Sec	Offence	Punishment
Sec 22	Obstruction	For obstructing the inspector or failing to produce registers etc. 3 months' imprisonment or fine up to Rs.500, or both.
Sec 23	Violation	For violation of the provisions of Act or the Rules, imprisonment Of 3 Months or fine up to Rs.1000. On continuing contravention, additional fine up to Rs.100 per day

Contract Labour (Regulation & Abolition Act, 1970 in Godrej

Industries Ltd

Sr. No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 7	Registration of Establishment in Form-I of Rules by Principal Employer	As Notified	The Company is Registered as a Principal Employer
2	Section 10	Register of Contract Labour in Form XIII	Continues	Register of Contract Labour is maintained
3	Rule 40	Provision of Facilities for Contract Labour	Within 7 days of Employment	All facilities are provided
4	Rule 41	Provision of Rest-rooms	Within 15 days of Employment	This facility is provided
5	Rule 42	Provision of Canteen	Within 60 days of Employment	This facility is provided
6	Rule 47	Charges for Foodstuffs	Display in Canteen	These are not displayed
7	Rule 49	Books of Accounts & Registers of Canteen	Continuous	Sree Durga Catterers will be asked to produce them
8	Rule 50	Audit of Canteen Books	Annual	The

		of Accounts		accounts will be asked to be audited
9	Rule 51	Provision of Latrines & Urinals	Continuous	This facility is provided
10	Rule 57	Provision of Washing Facility	Continuous	This facility is provided
11	Rule 58	Provision of First-aid Facility	Continuous	This facility is provided
12	Rule 74	Register of Contractors in Form XIII	Continuous	The Register is maintained
13	Rule 81	Display of Notice regarding payment to Contract labour	Continuous	Display not made
14	Rule 82	Half Yearly Returns in Form XXIV by Contractor	30 days from close of Half Year	Proof of submission not kept with the unit. Low Risk on company.
15	Rule 82	Annual Returns in Form XXV by Principal	15th February	Annual Returns is filed in time.

Employee's Provident Fund & Miscellaneous Provision Act, 1952 & the schemes

Eligibility

Any person who is employed for work of an establishment or employed through contractor in or in connection with the work of an establishment.

Applicability

- Every establishment which is factory engaged in any industry specified in Schedule 1 and in which 20 or more persons are employed.
- Any other establishment employing 20 or more persons whom Central Government may, by notification, specify in this behalf.
- Any establishment employing even less than 20 persons can be covered voluntarily u/s 1(4) of the Act.

Payment of Contribution

The employer shall pay the contribution payable to the EPF, DLI and Employees' Pension Fund in respect of the member of the Employees' Pension Fund employed by him directly by or through a contractor.

It shall be the responsibility of the principal employer to pay the contributions payable to the EPF, DLI and Employees' Pension Fund by himself in respect of the employees directly employed by him and also in respect of the employees directly employed by him and also in respect of the employees employed by or through a contractor.

Benefits

- Employees covered enjoy a benefit of Social Security in the form of an unattachable and unwithdrawable (except in severely restricted

circumstances like buying house, marriage/education, etc.) financial nest egg to which employees and employers contribute equally throughout the covered persons' employment.

- This sum is payable normally on retirement or death. Other Benefits include Employees' Pension Scheme and Employees' Deposit Linked Insurance Scheme.

Clarification about Contribution

After revision in wage ceiling from Rs.5000 to Rs.6500 w.e.f. 1.6.2001 per month, the government will continue to contribute 1.16% upto the actual wage of maximum Rs.6500 per month towards Employees' Pension Scheme. The employer's share in the Pension Scheme will be Rs.541 w.e.f. 1.6.2001.

Under Employees' Deposit-Linked Insurance Scheme the contribution @ 0.50% is required to be paid upto a maximum limit of Rs.6500.

The employer also will pay administrative charges @ 0.01% on maximum limit of Rs.6500 whereas an exempted establishment will pay inspection charges @ 0.005% on the total wages paid.

Notes:

The above clarification is given by taking wages up to a maximum of Rs.6500 towards wage (basic+DA).

Since an excluded employee i.e. drawing wages more than Rs.6500 can also become member of the Fund and the Schemes on joint request and if, for instance, such an employee is getting Rs.10, 000 per month, his share towards provident fund contribution will be Rs.1200 e.g. 12% and employer's share towards provident fund contribution will be Rs.659 and Rs.541 towards Employees' Pension Fund.

Damages

Less than 2 months	17% per annum
Two months and above but less than up to four months	22% per annum
Four months and above but less than up to six months	27% per annum

Rate of the contribution

SCHEME	EMPLOYEE'S	EMPLOYER'S	CENTRAL GOVT'S
Provident Fund Scheme	12%	Amount > 8.33% (in case where contribution is 12% of 10%) 10% (in case of certain Establishments as per details given earlier)	NIL
Insurance Scheme	NIL	0.5	NIL
Pension Scheme	NIL	8.33% (Diverted out of Provident Fund)	1.16%

Penal Provision

- Liable to be arrested without warrants being a cognizable offence.
- Defaults by employer in paying contributions or inspection/administrative charges attract imprisonment up to 3 years and fines up to Rs.10, 000 (S.14).
- For any retrospective application, all dues have to be paid by employer with damages up to 100% of arrears.

Employee's Provident Fund & Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952 & the Schemes in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 33	Declaration from Employee in Form 2	15th of following month of employment	Form 2 is submitted along with Returns. There is a delay of few days.
2	Section 36	Declaration from Employee in Form 5	15th of following month of employment	Form 5 is submitted along with Returns. There is a delay of few days.
3	Section 35	Preparation of Contribution Cards in Form 3 by Employer	After receipt of number from PF Office	These are issued on initial engagement.
4	Section 36	Monthly Return in Form 12,12-A	25th of next Month	Monthly Returns are filed in time.
5	Section 36(4)	Inspection Book	To be maintained at factory/office	Inspection Book is lying with PF Commissioner according to the management.
6	Section	Accounts of	Continuous	Accounts are

	36(5)	Payments Made		properly maintained.
7	Section 36-A	Particulars of Ownership	On Establishment	Duly sent
8	Section 40-A	Obtaining Annual PF A/c Statement Slips	Yearly	Slips are received up to 2005-06.
9	Section 43	Submission of Contribution Cards in Form 6	Within 1 month of employment	Being sent
10	Para 38(3) Employees Provident Fund Scheme 1952	Annual Return	Form 6A to be filed within 30 days of close of accounting year	Due date was 31st March. However the Return was filed on 25th April. The Return was delayed due to transitional problems from MFG-PRO to SAP.

Employee Exchange (Compulsory Notification of Vacancies) Act, 1959 the rule.

Object of the Act

To provide for the compulsory notification of vacancies to employment exchanges.

Applicability of the Act

By notification in the Official Gazette, appoint in this behalf for such State and different dates may be appointed for different states or for different areas of a State.

When Act is not applicable (Sec. 3)

- Any employment in agriculture, horticulture etc.
- Any employment in domestic service.
- Any employment, the total duration of which is less than three months.
- Any employment to do unskilled office work.
- Any employment connected with the staff of Parliament.

Notification of vacancies to Employment Exchanges (Sec. 4)

- Before filling up any vacancy as prescribed.
- Employer not obliged to recruit the person through employment exchange.
- To notify the vacancies to such employment exchanges as may be prescribed.

Furnishing information and returns (Sec. 5)

The employer in every establishment in public sector in that State or area shall furnish such information or return as may be prescribed in

relation to vacancies that have occurred or are about to occur in that establishment, to such employment exchanges as may be prescribed.

Time limit for notification of vacancies & selection (Rules 5)

- At least 15 days before the applicants will be interviewed or tested.
- Employer to furnish the result of selection within 15 days.

Submission of Returns (Rules 6)

- Quarterly in Form ER-I
- BIENNIAL Return Form ER-II
- Within 30 days by 30th June, 31st March, 30th September & 31st December.

PENALTIES (Rules 7)

- An employer contravening the provisions of Sec.4 (1) or (2).
- Fine upto Rs.500 for first offence and for every subsequent offence fine Rs.1000.
- If any person –
 - Required to furnish any information or return –
 - Refuses or neglects to furnish such information or return, or
 - Furnishes or causes to be furnished any information or return which he knows to be false, or
 - Refuses to answer, or gives a false answer to any question necessary for obtaining any information required to be furnished under section 5; or
- Impedes the right of access to relevant records or documents or the right of entry conferred by section 6; he shall be punishable for the first offence with fine upto Rs.250 and for every subsequent offence with fine upto Rs.250 and for every subsequent offence with fine upto Rs.500.

Employment Exchange (Compulsory Notification of Vacancies)

Act, 1959 & the Rule in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr. No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 4	Notification of Vacancy	15 days before interview	Notification has been made.
2	Section 5	Return	Before filling up vacancy	Not applicable
3	Rule 6	Quarterly Returns in Form ER-I	Within 30 days from the end of quarter	Quarterly Returns are filed in time.
4	Section 4	Notification of Vacancy	15 days before interview	Notification has been made.

Industrial employment (standing orders) Act, 1946

Applicability of the Act (Sec.1)

Every industrial establishment wherein 100 or more (in many States it is 50 or more). Any industry covered by Bombay Industrial Relations Act, 1946. Industrial establishment covered by M.P. Industrial Employment (Standing Orders) Act, 1961.

Matters to be provided in Standing orders (Sec.2 (g), 3(2) and Rule 2A)

- Classification of workmen, e.g., whether permanent, temporary, apprentices, probationers, or badlis.
- Manner of intimating to workmen periods and hours of work, holidays, pay-days and wage rates.
- Shift working.
- Attendance and late coming.
- Conditions of, procedure in applying for, and the authority which may grant, leave and holidays.
- Requirement to enter premises by certain gates, and liability to search.
- Closing and re-opening of sections of the industrial establishments, and temporary stoppages of work and the right and liabilities of the employer and workmen arising there from.
- Termination of employment, and the notice thereof to be given by employer and workmen.
- Suspension or dismissal for misconduct, and acts or omissions which constitute misconduct.
- Means of redressal for workmen against unfair treatment or wrongful exactions by the employer or his agents or servant

Additional Matters

Service Record – Matters relating to service card, token tickets, certification of service, change of residential address of workers and record of age Confirmation Age of retirement Transfer Medical aid in case of Accident Medical Examination Secrecy Exclusive service.

Conditions for Certification of Standing Orders

- Every matter to be set out as per Schedule and Rule 2A.
- The standing orders to be in conformity with the provisions of the Act.

Submissions of Draft Standing Orders (Sec.3)

Within six months from the date when the Act becomes applicable to an industrial establishment. Five copies of the draft Standing Orders are to be submitted to the Certifying Officer under the Act.

Procedure for Certification of Standing Orders (Sec.5)

Certifying Officer to forward a copy of draft standing orders to the trade union or in the absence of union, to the workmen of the industry. The trade union or the other representatives, as the case may be, are to be heard.

Date of Operation of Standing Orders (Sec.7)

On the date of expiry of 30 days from certification or on the expiry of 7 days from authentication of Standing Orders.

Posting of Standing Orders (Sec.9)

The text of the standing orders as finally certified shall prominently be posted in English or in the language understood by majority of workmen on special board at or near the entrance for majority of workers.

Payment of Subsistence Allowance to the Suspended Workers
(Sec.10-A)

At the rate of fifty per cent, of the wages which the workman was entitled to immediately preceding the date of such suspension, for the first ninety days of suspension.

At the rate of seventy-five percent of such wages for the remaining period of suspension if the delay in the completion of disciplinary proceedings against such workman is not directly attributable to the conduct such workman.

Temporary application of Model Standing Orders (Sec.12-A)

Temporary application of model standing orders shall be deemed to be adopted till the standing orders as submitted are certified.

PENALTIES

- Failure of employer to submit draft Standing Orders fine of Rs.5000 and Rs.200 for every day on continuation of offence.
- Fine of Rs.100 on contravention and on continuation of offence Rs.25 for every day.

**The Industrial Employment (Standing Orders) Act, 1946/Rules in
Godrej Industries Ltd**

Sr. No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 3	Submission of Draft Standing Orders in Form-I	Within 6 months	Submitted
2	Section 8	Submission of Final Standing Orders in Form-III	Model Standing Orders to be certified	Duly submitted
3	Schedule I, I-A	Compliance with Standing Orders	Display to be made	Kept in the Record Room

Boilers Act, 1923 (Indian)

Applicability of the Act (Sec.1)

An Act to consolidate and amend the law relating to steam-boilers.

Definitions

“Accident” means an explosion of a boiler or steam-pipe or any damage to a boiler or steam-pipe which is calculated to weaken the strength there of so as to render it liable to explode “Boiler” means any closed vessel exceeding (22.75 liters) in capacity which is used expressly for generating steam under pressure and includes any mounting or other fitting attached to such vessel which is wholly or partly under pressure when steam is shut off.

Application of Act to feed-pipes [Sec-2(A)]

Every reference in this Act (except where the word “steam-pipe” is used in clause (f) of Section-2) to a steam-pipe shall be deemed to include also a reference to a feed-pipe or feed-pipes, respectively.

Application of Act to economizers [Sec-2(B)]

Every reference in this Act to a boiler or boilers (except in clause (ccc) of Section 2, shall be deemed to include also a reference to an economiser or economizer, respectively.

Limitation of application

- In any steamship as defined in Section 3 of the Indian Steamships Act, 1884 (7 of 1884), or in any steam-vessel as defined in Section 2 of the Inland Steam-Vessels Act, 1917 (1 of 1917)
- Belonging to, or under the control of, the Army, Navy or Air Force.

- Appertaining to a sterilizer or disinfectant of a type such as is commonly used in hospitals, if the boiler does not exceed [ninety-one liters] in capacity.

Prohibition of use of unregistered or uncertified boiler (Sec-6)

- Unless it has been registered in accordance with the provision of this Act.
- In the case of any boiler which has been transferred from one State to another, until the transfer has been reported in the prescribed manner.
- Unless a certificate or provisional order authorizing the use of the boiler is for the time being in force under this Act.
- At a pressure higher than the maximum pressure recorded in such certificate or provisional order.
- Where the State Government has made rules requiring that boilers shall be in charge of persons holding the certificate required by such rules.

Renewal of certificate (Sec-8)

A certificate authorizing the use of a boiler shall cease to be in force:-

- On the expiry of the period for which it was granted.
- When any accident occurs to the boiler.
- When the boiler is moved, the boiler not being a vertical boiler the heating surface of which is less than [18.58 square meters], or a portable or vehicular boiler.
- When any structural alteration, addition or renewal is made in or to the boiler.
- If the chief Inspector in any particular case so directs, when any structural alteration, addition or renewal is made in or to any steam-pipe attached to the boiler.

- On the communication to the owner of the boiler of an order of the Chief Inspector or Inspector prohibiting its use on the ground that it or any steam-pipe attached there to is in a dangerous condition.

Use of boiler pending grant of certificate (Sec-10)

Notwithstanding anything here in before contained, when the period of a certificate relating to a boiler has expired, the owner shall, provided that he has applied before the expiry of that period for a renewal of the certificate, be entitled to use the boiler at the maximum pressure entered in the former certificate pending the issue of orders on the application.

Revocation of certificate or provisional order (Sec-11)

The Chief Inspector may at any time withdraw or revoke any certificate or provisional order on the report of an Inspector or otherwise:-

- If there is reason to believe that the certificate or provisional order has been fraudulently obtained or has been granted erroneously or without sufficient examination.
- If the boiler in respect of which it has been granted has sustained injury or has ceased to be in good condition.
- Where the State Government has made rules requiring that boiler shall be in charge of persons holding [certificate of proficiency or competency], if the boiler is in charge of a person not holding the certificate required by such rules.

Alterations and renewals to boilers (Sec-12)

No structural alteration, addition or renewal shall be made in or to any boiler registered under this Act unless such alteration, addition or renewal has been sanctioned in writing by the Chief Inspector.

Alternations and renewals to steam-pipes (Sec-13)

Before the owner of any boiler registered under this Act makes any structural alteration, addition or renewal in or to any steam-pipe attached to the boiler, he shall transmit to the Chief Inspector a report in writing of his intention, and shall send there with such particulars of the proposed alternation, addition or renewal as may be prescribed.

Duty of owner at Examination (Sec-14)

- To afford to the Inspector all reasonable facilities for the examination and all such information as may reasonably be required of him.
- To have the boiler properly prepared and ready for examination in the prescribed manner.
- In the case of an application for the registration of a boiler, to provide such drawings, specifications, certificate and other particulars as may be prescribed.

Power of entry (Sec-17)

An Inspector may, for the purpose of inspecting or examining a boiler or any steam-pipe attached thereto of seeing that any provision of this Act or of any regulation or rule made here under has been or is being observed, at all reasonable times enter any place or building within the limits of the area for which he has been appointed in which he has reason to believe that a boiler is in use.

Report of accidents (Sec-18)

- If any accident occurs to a boiler or steam-pipe, the owner or person in charge there of shall, within twenty-four hours of the accident, report the same in writing to the Inspector. Every such report shall contain a true description of the nature of the accident and of the injury, if any, caused there by to the boiler or to the

steam-pipe or to any person, and shall be in sufficient details to enable the Inspector to judge the gravity of the accident.

- Every person shall be bound to answer truly to the best of his knowledge and ability every question put to him in writing by the Inspector as to the cause, nature or extent of the accident.

Penalties

Minor Penalties (Sec-22)

Any owner of a boiler who refuses or without reasonable excuse neglects:-

- To surrender a provisional order as required by section 9.
- To produce a certificate or provisional order when duly called upon to do so under Section 15.
- To make over to the new owner of a boiler a certificate or provisional order as required by Section 16.

Penalties for illegal use of boiler (Sec-23)

Any owner of a boiler who, in any case in which a certificate or provisional order is required for the use of the boiler under this Act, use the boiler either without any such certificate or order being in force or at a higher pressure than that allowed there by, shall be punishable with fine which may extend to five hundred rupees, and in case of a continuing offence, with an additional fine which may extend to one hundred rupees for each day after the first day in regard to which he is convicted of having persisted in the offence.

Other penalties (Sec-24); - Any person who-

- Use or permits to be used a boiler of which he is the owner and which has been transferred from one State to another without such transfer having been reported as required by Section 6.

- Being the owner of a boiler fails to cause the register number allotted to the boiler under this Act to be marked on the boiler as required by sub-section (6) of Section 7.
- Makes any structural alteration, addition or renewal in or to a boiler without first obtaining the sanction of the Chief Inspector when so required by section 12 or to a steam-pipe without first informing the Chief Inspector, when so required by Section 13.
- Fails to reports an accident to a boiler or steam-pipe when so required by Section 18.
- Tamper with a safety-valve of a boiler so as to render it inoperative at the maximum pressure at which the use of the boiler is authorized under this Act.
- Allows another person to go inside a boiler without effectively disconnecting the same in the prescribed manner from any steam or hot-water connection with fine which may extend to five hundred rupees.

Penalty for tampering with register mark (Sub-25)

- Whoever removes, alters, defaces, renders invisible or otherwise tampers with the register number marked on a boiler in accordance with the provisions of this Act or any Act repealed here by, shall be punishable with fine which may extend to five hundred rupees.
- Whoever fraudulently marks upon a boiler a register number which has not been allotted to it under this Act or any Act repealed hereby, shall be punishable with imprisonment which may extend to two years, or with fine, or with both.

Limitation and previous sanction for prosecutions (Sec-26)

No Prosecution for an offence made punishable by or under this Act shall be instituted except within [twenty-four months] from the date

of the commission of the offence, and no such prosecution shall be instituted without the previous sanction of the Chief Inspector.

Trial of offences (Sec-27)

No offence made punishable by or under this Act shall be tried by a Court inferior to that of a Presidency Magistrate or a Magistrate of the first class.

Indian Boilers Act, 1923 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr. No	Section/Rule	Activities	Due Date/Update	Remarks
1	Section 7	Registration	Before Use	Registration is being done, but Copy of Registration Certificate is not available.
2	Section 8	Renewal of Registration	On Occurrence	Renewal is made from time to time before expiry.

Equal Remuneration Act, 1976

Definition

- “appropriate Government” means,-
- In relation to any employment carried on by or under the authority of the Central Government or railway administration, or in relation to a banking company, a mine, oilfield or major port or any corporation established by or under a Central Act, the Central Government.
- In relation to any other employment, the State Government.
- “Commencement of this Act” means, in relation to an establishment or employment, the date on which this Act comes into force in respect of that establishment or employment.

Complaints regarding contravention of the Act (Sec-3)

- Every complaint under clause (a) of sub-section (1) of section 7 shall be made in triplicate, in Form “A” to the Authority.
- A single complaint may be made by, or on behalf of, or in relation to, a group of workers, if they are employed in the same establishment and the complaint relates to the same contravention.
- A complaint may be made by the worker himself or herself or by any legal practitioner, or by any official of a registered Trade Union, authorized in writing to appear and act on his or her behalf or by any Inspector appointed under Section 9 or by any other person acting with the permission of the Authority.

Claim regarding non-payment of wages (Sec-4)

- Every claim under clause (b) of sub-section (1) of Section 7 shall be made by petition in triplicate, in Form “B” to the Authority.

- A single petition may be made by, or on behalf of, or in relation to, a group of workers, if they are employed in the same establishment and their claims are of the same nature.
- A claim may be made by the worker himself or herself or by any legal practitioner, or by any official of a registered Trade Union, authorized in writing to appear and act on his or her behalf or by any Inspector appointed under Section 9 or by any other person acting with the permission of the Authority.

Authorization (Sec- 5)

The authorization referred to in sub-rule (3) of Rule 3 or sub-rule (3) of Rule 4 shall be in Form “C” which shall be presented to the Authority to whom the complaint or the claim, as the case may be, is made along with such complaint or claim and shall form part of the record.

Equal Remuneration Act, 1976 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/ Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 8/Rule 6	Maintenance of Register in Form D	Continuous	Register is maintained in Form D.

Maternity benefit Act, 1961

Object of the Act

To protect the dignity of motherhood and the dignity of a new person's birth by providing for the full and healthy maintenance of the woman and her child at this important time when she is not working

Coverage of the Act

Upon all women employees either employed directly or through contractor except domestic women employees employed in mines, factories, plantations and also in other establishments if the State Government so decides. Therefore, if the State Government decides to apply this Act to women employees in shops and commercial establishments, they also will get the benefit of this Act. Bihar, Punjab Haryana, West Bengal, U.P., Orissa and Andhra have done so.

Conditions for eligibility of benefits

Women indulging temporary of unmarried are eligible for maternity benefit when she is expecting a child and has worked for her employer for at least 80 days in the 12 months immediately preceding the date of her expected delivery.

Cash Benefits:

Leave with average pay for six weeks before the delivery.

Leave with average pay for six weeks after the delivery.

A medical bonus of Rs.25 if the employer does not provide free medical care to the woman

An additional leave with pay up to one month if the woman shows proof of illness due to the pregnancy, delivery, miscarriage, or premature birth.

In case of miscarriage, six weeks leave with average pay from the date of miscarriage.

Non Cash Benefits/Privilege:

- Light work for ten weeks (six weeks plus one month) before the date of her expected delivery, if she asks for it.
- Two nursing breaks in the course of her daily work until the child are 15 months old.
- No discharge or dismissal while she is on maternity leave.
- No change to her disadvantage in any of the conditions of her employment while on maternity leave.
- Pregnant women discharged or dismissed may still claim maternity benefit from the employer.
- Exception: Women dismissed for gross misconduct lose their right under the Act for Maternity Benefit

Conditions for eligibility of benefits (Sec. 5)

- Ten weeks before the date of her expected delivery, she may ask the employer to give her light work for a month. At that time she should produce a certificate that she is pregnant.
- She should give written notice to the employer about seven weeks before the date of her delivery that she will be absent for six weeks before and after her delivery. She should also name the person to whom payment will be made in case she can not take it herself.
- She should take the payment for the first six weeks before she goes on leave.
- She will get payment for the six weeks after child-birth within 48 hours of giving proof that she has had a child.
- She will be entitled to two nursing breaks of fifteen minutes each in the course of her daily work till her child is fifteen months old.
- Her employer cannot discharge her or change her conditions of service while she is on maternity leave.

Leave for Miscarriage & Tubectomy Operation

- Leave with wages at the rate of maternity benefit, for a period of six weeks immediately following the day of her miscarriage or her medical termination of pregnancy.
- Entitled to leave with wages at the rate of maternity benefit for a period of two weeks immediately following the day of her tubectomy operation.

Leave for illness arising out of pregnancy etc. (Sec.10)

A woman suffering from illness arising out of pregnancy, delivery, premature birth of child (Miscarriage, medical termination of pregnancy or tubectomy operation) is entitled, in addition to the period of absence allowed to her leave with wages at the rate of maternity benefit for a maximum period of one month.

Prohibition of dismissal during absence of pregnancy (Sec.12)

Discharge or dismissal of a woman employed during or on account of such absence or to give notice or discharge or dismissal on such a day that the notice will expire during such absence or to vary her disadvantage.

Discharge or dismissal during or on account of such absence or to give notice of discharge or dismissal on such a day that the notice will expire during such absence, or to vary to her disadvantage any of the conditions of her service.

At the time during her pregnancy, if the woman but for such discharge or dismissal would have been entitled to maternity benefit or medical bonus, etc.

Not barred in case of dismissal for cross misconduct.

Failure to Display Extract of Act

Imprisonment may extend to one year or fine.

Forfeiture of maternity benefit (Sec.18)

- If permitted by her employer to absent herself under the provisions of section 6 for any period during such authorized absence, she shall forfeit her claim to the maternity benefit for such period.
- For discharging or dismissing such a woman during or on account of her absence from work, the employer shall be punishable with imprisonment which shall not be less than 3 months, but it will extend to one year and will find, but not exceeding Rs.5, 000.

Maternity Benefit Act, in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 18	Display of Abstract of the Act	Continuous	Display not made.
2	Section 20	Registers as Prescribed	Continuous	Register is properly maintained.
3	Rule 12	Supply of Forms	Continuous	Return is submitted in time.

Factories Act, 1948

Applicability of the Act

Any premises whereon 10 or more persons with the aid of power or 20 or more workers are/were without aid of power working on any day preceding 12 months, wherein Manufacturing process is being carried on.

Employer to ensure health of workers pertaining to (Sec-11 to 20)

- **Cleanliness Disposal of wastes and effluents:** - Every occupier is required to keep the factory premises clean and free from waste and effluvia arising from any drains, privy or other nuisance And He was to make proper arrangement for sweeping, cleaning and disposal of waste and effluent on regular basis. Secondly all inside walls, partitions, staircases, roof are required to be white washed and all doors, window frames, shutters etc are required to be painted from time to time as per rules.
- **Ventilation and temperature dust and fume:** - The factory premises should be adequately ventilated by circulation of fresh air and comfortable temperature should be maintained in every workroom.
- **Overcrowding artificial humidification lighting:** - The state government may rules for the standards of humidification in factories where humidity in the air is artificially increased.
- **Drinking water Spittoons:** - Wholesome drinking water at suitable points and cool water arrangement during hot season is required to be provided And Sufficient numbers of spittoons are to be provided

and maintained in a clean and hygienic condition at suitable locations.

Registration & Renewal of Factories (Sec-6)

To be granted by Chief Inspector of Factories on submission of prescribed form, fee and plan.

Safety Measures (Sec - 21 to 40)

- **Fencing of machinery:** - Fencing of dangerous and moving machinery, sufficient place for operating machinery, guarding of all machinery etc required. The employer should take necessary steps to prevent danger and to ensure maximum safe working.
- **Work on near machinery in motion:** - When any part of machinery is required to be examined or any operation is to be carried out while in motion, it should be made or carried out only by a specially trained person wearing tight fitting clothing. Women or child worker is not allowed to clean or lubricant any part of moving machinery.
- **Employment prohibition of young person's on dangerous machines:** - Young person (15 to 18 yrs) are not supposed to work in any dangerous machine without adequate training and supervision.
- **Striking gear and devices for cutting off power:** - Suitable striking gear or other such devices for the movement of driving belts of any transmission machinery and proper locking of device which can shift inadvertently from off to one position is required.
- **Self-acting machines:** - The traversing part of self acting machine or material carried thereon shall be at specified distance from the fixed structure or space for passing of employees.
- **Casing of new machinery:** - All power driven machinery in a factory should be so sunk or encased or effectively guarded to prevent danger.

- **Prohibition of employment of women and children near cotton-openers:** - No women or child to be employed in any part of cotton factory where cotton opener is at work.
- **Hoists and lifts:** - All hoists lift and other lifting devices should be of good mechanical construction, sound material with adequate strength and free from defect. All these devices are required to be properly maintained and thoroughly examined by competent person at least once in six months with recorded particulars in prescribed register. The maximum safe working load should be marled on every hoist or lift. The cage of such device should be fitted with gate with interlock.

Welfare Measures (Sec- 42 to 49)

- **Washing facilities:** - Adequate and suitable facilities for washing should be provided and maintained and should be separately for man and women workers.
- **Facilities for storing and drying clothing:** - There should be suitable place for keeping clothing not worn during working hours and for the drying of wet clothing.
- **Facilities for sitting:** - Sitting arrangement for workers who are required to work in standing position in order that they may take short rest in the course of their work.
- **First-aid appliances** – First aid boxes or cupboards equipped with the prescribed contents (at least one box for every 150 workers) shall be provided and maintained so as to readily accessible during working hours.
- **Canteen:** - This facility is compulsory where 250 or more worker 150 or more workers are employed. There should be sufficient lighting, ventilated. It shall be of the prescribed size, equipped with necessary furniture, utensils etc and to be operated on non profit basis.
- **Shelters, rest room and lunch room:** - This facility is required where 150 or more workers are employed. There should be sufficient

lighting, ventilation, furnished and kept in cool and clean condition. However where canteen is provided, the provision of rest/shelter/lunch room is not obligatory.

- **Crèches:** - when there are 30 or more women workers employees, the crèche facility is compulsory with sufficient lighting, ventilation and should be maintained in clean and sanitary condition under the charge of trained women. Provision for washroom, supply of milk, refreshment is required. The facility for feeding at necessary intervals by their mother should be made as per rules.
- **Welfare Officer:** - Where 500 or more worker are employed, the appointment of welfare officer is compulsory. The state government may prescribe his duties, qualification etc.

Working Hours, Spread Over & Overtime of Adults (Sec- 51, 54 to 56, 59 & 60)

- Weekly hours not more than 48.
- Daily hours, not more than 9 hours
- Intervals for rest at least ½ hour on working for 5 hours.
- Spread over not more than 10½ hours.
- Overlapping shifts prohibited.
- Extra wages for overtime double than normal rate of wages.
- Restrictions on employment of women before 6AM and beyond 7 PM.

Employment of Young Persons (Sec- 51, 54 to 56, 59 & 60)

- Prohibition of employment of young children e.g. 14 years.
- Non-adult workers to carry tokens e.g. certificate of fitness.
- Working hours for children not more than 4 ½ hrs. And not permitted to work during night shift.

Annual Leave with Wages (Sec-79)

A worker having worked for 240 days @ one day for every 20 days and for a child one day for working of 15 days.

Accumulation of leave for 30 days.

Offence and Penalties

OFFENCE	PENALTIES Sec.92 to
For contravention of the Provisions of the Act or Rules	Imprisonment upto 2 years or fine upto Rs.1, 00,000 or both
On Continuation of contravention	Rs.1000 per day
On contravention of Chapter IV pertaining to safety or dangerous operations.	Not less than Rs.25000 in case of death. Not less than Rs.5000 in case of serious injuries.
Subsequent contravention of some provisions	Imprisonment up to 3 years or fine not less than Rs.10, 000 which may extend to Rs.2, 00,000.
Obstructing Inspectors	Imprisonment up to 6 months or fine up to Rs.10, 000 or both.
Wrongful disclosing result pertaining to results of analysis.	Imprisonment up to 6 months or fine up to Rs.10, 000 or both.
For contravention of the provisions of Sec.41B, 41C and 41H pertaining to compulsory disclosure of information by occupier, specific responsibility of occupier or right of workers to work imminent danger.	Imprisonment up to 7 years with fine up to Rs.2, 00,000 and on continuation fine @ Rs.5, 000 per day. Imprisonment of 10 years when contravention continues for one year.

Factory Act, 1948 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 28 (a)	Register of maintenance of Hoists and Lifts	Once in 6 months	Register is maintained in Form 10.
2	Section 29 (a)	Register of maintenance for lifting machines, chains, ropes and lifting tackle [s.29(a)]	Once in 12 months	Same as above.
3	Section 62	Register of Adult Workers	Regularly	Register of Adult Workers is maintained.
4	Section 63	Register of Child Workers	Regularly	Not Applicable.
5	Rule 15	Register of Health	Regularly	Register of Health is maintained.
6	Rule 17	Register of Maintenance and White Washing (Factory)	Washable-Once in 3 years. Non-Washable - Once in 5 Years	Register for Factory & Toilets, Urinals is combined & maintained manually.

7	Rule 48	Register of Maintenance and White Washing (Toilets/ Latrines)	Once in 4 mths	Same as above.
8	Rule 68 A	Register of workers attending to Prime Movers	Regularly	No Prime Movers.
9	Rule 61 A	Register with details of Gas Holders	Regularly	No Gas Holders.
10	Rule 111	Register of Accidents	Regularly	Register of Accidents is maintained.
11	Rule 84	Register of Compensatory Holidays	Monthly	Register is maintained as a Salary Register.
12	Rule 85	Muster-roll for exempt factories	Regularly	Not Applicable.
13	Rule 84	Register of Leave and Wages	Regularly	Maintained regularly.
14	Rule 101	Register of Leave and Wages for s.84 Factories	Regularly	Not Applicable.
15	Rule 107	Annual Returns	On or Before 1st Feb.	Annual Return for Calender Year 2006 is late by 14 days.
16	Rule 107	Half Yearly Returns	On or Before 15th July	Half Yearly Returns are filed in time.
17	Rule 107	List of Holidays	Before End of Each	List of

			Year	Holidays is submitted to the Factories Inspectorate in December 2006.
18	Rule 110	Muster-roll of Employees	Monthly	Attendance Register is maintained.
19	Rule 111	Register of Dangerous Occurrences	15th Feb.	No Dangerous Occurrences
20	Section 7	Notice by Occupier	15 days before Occupation	Duly sent.
21	Section 7	Resumes factory working which were stopped	30 days prior	Not Applicable.
22	Section 7	Change in Manager	Within 7 days	Not Applicable.
23	Section 61	Notice of period of work for Adult workers	To be displayed on notice board	Not displayed
24	Section 72	Notice of Period of work for child workers	To be displayed on notice board	Not Applicable.
25	Rule 3	Approval of Plans	Before Setting up Factory	Duly sent for EOU.
26	Rule 5	Application for Registration and grant of License	After Commencement	Duly made.
27	Rule 61 A	Report of Person Competent to examine	Once in 12 months	Not Applicable.

		Gas Holder		
28	Rule 70 A	Notice of First Aid	To be displayed near First Aid Box	Notice of First Aid has been displayed.
29	Rule 103	Notice of Accidents and Dangerous Occurrences	Within 48 hours of Occurrence	Accidents are notified to the Factories Inspectorate .
30	Rule 104	Notice of Poisoning or Disease	Within 48 hours of Occurrence	Not Applicable.
31	Rule 113	Notice Regarding Closure	On date of Decision	Not Applicable.
32	Section 49	Welfare Officer	500 or more workers	Not Applicable.
33	Section 40-B	Safety Officer	1000 or more workers	Not Applicable.
34	Rule 112	Inspection Book in Form 31	Continuous	Duly maintained

Minimum Wages Act, 1948

Object of the Act

To provide for fixing minimum rates of wages in certain employments.

Fixation of Minimum Rates of Wages (Sec.3)

- The appropriate government to fix minimum rates of wages. The employees employed in Para 1 or B of Schedule either at 2 or either part of notification u/s 27.
- To make review at such intervals not exceeding five years the minimum rates or so fixed and revised the minimum rates.

Government can also fix Minimum Wages for

- Time work
- Piece work at piece rate
- Piece work for the purpose of securing to such employees on a time work basis
- Overtime work done by employees for piece work or time rate workers.

Minimum Rates of Wages (Sec.4)

Such as Basic rates of wages etc. Variable DA and Value of other concessions etc.

Procedure for fixing and revising Minimum Rates of Wages (Sec.5)

Appointing Committee issue of Notification etc.

Overtime (Sec.5)

To be fixed by the hour, by the day or by such a longer wage-period works on any day in excess of the number of hours constituting normal working day.

Payment for every hour or for part of an hour so worked in excess at the overtime rate double of the ordinary rate of (1½ times or for agriculture labour)

Composition of Committee (Sec.9)

Representation of employer and employee in schedule employer in equal number and independent persons not exceeding 1/3rd or its total number one such person to be appointed by the Chairman.

Payment of Minimum Rates of Wages (Sec.12)

Employer to pay to every employee engaged in schedule employment at rate not less than minimum rates of wages as fixed by Notification by not making deduction other than prescribed.

Fixing Hours for Normal Working (Sec.13)

- Shall constitute a normal working day inclusive of one or more specified intervals.
- To provide for a day of rest in every period of seven days with remuneration.
- To provide for payment for work on a day of rest at a rate not less than the overtime rate.
- Wages of workers who works for less than normal working days (Sec.15)
- Save as otherwise hereinafter provided; be entitled to receive wages in respect of work done by him on that day as if he had worked for a full normal working day.

Wages for two class of work (Sec. 16)

Where an employee does two or more classes of work to each of which a different minimum rate of wages is applicable, wages at not less than the minimum rate in respect of each such class.

Claims by employees (Sec.16)

- To be filed by before authority constituted under the Act within **6** months.
- Compensation up to **10** times on under or non-payment of wages.

Minimum time rate wages for piece work (Sec. 17)

Not less than minimum rates wages as fixed.

Maintenance of registers and records (Sec.18)

Register of Fines – Form I Rule 21(4)

Annual Returns – Form III Rule 21 (4-A)

Register for Overtime – Form IV Rule 25

Register of Wages–Form X, Wages slip–Form XI, Muster Roll–Form V Rule 26

Representation of register – for three year Rule 26-A.

PENALITIES Sec. 20

PENALITIES	Offence	Punishment
Sec. 20	For paying less than minimum rates of wages	Imprisonment up to 6 months or with fine up to Rs.500/-
	For contravention of any provisions pertaining to fixing hours for normal working day etc.	Imprisonment up to 6 months or with fine up to Rs.500/-

Minimum Wages Act, 1948 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 18	Maintenance of Registers in Form X	Continuous	Only Salary Register is maintained.
2	Section 18	Display Minimum Fixed Wages in Form IX-A	Continuous	Same as above.
3	Rule 21	Register of Fines and Deductions in Form I/II	Continuous	Same as above.
4	Rule 25	Register of Overtime	Continuous	Same as above.
5	Rule 26	Wage Slips to Employees in Form XI	Continuous	Wage Slips are provided to all employees.
6	Rule 26 (5)	Muster Roll in Form 5	Continuous	Attendance Register is maintained.

Payment of Bonus Act, 1965

Applicability of Act

- Every factory where in **10** or more persons are employed with the aid of power.
- An establishment in which **20** or more persons are employed without the aid of power on any day during an accounting year.

Establishment

Establishment includes Departments, undertakings and branches, etc.

Components of Bonus [Sec.2 (21)]

Salary or wages includes dearness allowance but no other allowances e.g. over-time, house rent, incentive or commission.

Separate establishment (Sec.3)

If profit and loss accounts are prepared and maintained in respect of any such department or undertaking or branch, then such department or undertaking or branch is treated as a separate establishment.

Computation of gross profit (Sec.4)

For banking company, as per First Schedule. Others, as per Second Schedule.

Computation of available surplus (Sec.5)

- Income taxes and direct taxes as payable.
- Depreciation as per section 32 of Income Tax Act.
- Development rebate, investment or development allowance.

Eligibility of Bonus (Sec.8)

An employee will be entitled only when he has worked for **30** working days in that year.

Disqualification & Deduction of Bonus (Sec. 9 & 18)

- On dismissal of an employee for Fraud.
- Riotous or violent behavior while on the premises of the establishment.

- Theft, misappropriation or sabotage of any property of the establishment.
- Misconduct of causing financial loss to the Employer to the extent that bonus can be deducted for that year.

Payment of Minimum Bonus (Sec.10)

8.33% of the salary or Rs.100 (on completion of 5 years after 1st Accounting year even if there is no profit)

Set-off and Set-on (Sec. 15)

As per Schedule IV.

Time Limit for Payment of Bonus (Sec.19)

Within 8 months from the close of accounting year.

Maintenance of Registers and Records etc. (Sec.26, Rule 4)

- A register showing the computation of the **allocable surplus** referred to in clause (4) of section 2, in form A.
- A register showing the **set-on and set-off** of the allocable surplus, under section 15, in form B
- A register showing the details of **the amount of bonus due** to each of the employees, the deductions under section 17 and 18 and the amount actually disbursed, in form C.

Act not to apply to certain classes of employees (Sec.32)

Act not applicable to certain employees of LIC, General Insurance, Dockyards, Red Cross, Universities & Educational Institutions, Chambers of Commerce, Social Welfare Institutions, Building Contractors, etc.

PENALTY (Sec. 28)

For contravention of any provision of the Act or the Rule	Upto 6 months or with fine upto Rs.1000.
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Payment of Bonus Act, 1965 in Godrej Industries Ltd

S r. N o	Section/ Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 19	Timely payment of Bonus	On or before 30th November	Payment is made in time.
2	Rule 5/Section 19	Annual Returns in Form D	30th Dec	Annual Return is filed on 08- 11-2006.
3	Section 26/Rule	Maintenance of Registers in Form A/B/C	Continuous	Form C is maintained.

Payment of Gratuity Act, 1936

Applicability (Sec-1)

Every factory, mine, oil field, plantation, port, railways, company, shop, establishment or educational institutions employing 10 or more employees.

Calculation Piece-rated employee

@ 15 days wages for every completed year on an average of 3 months' wages.

Calculation Seasonal employee

@7 days' wages for every completed year of service.

Wages for Calculation (Sec 2{s})

@ 15 days' wages for every completed year as if the month comprises of 26 days at the last drawn wages.

Employee Sec-2 (e)

All employees irrespective of status or salary Entitlement On completion of five years' service except in case of death or disablement.

Qualifying period

On rendering of 5 years' service, termination, resignation or retirement.

Maximum Ceiling Sec 4(3) Rs.3, 50,000

Forfeiture of Gratuity Sec 4(6)

- On termination of an employee for moral turpitude or riotous or disorderly behavior.
- Wholly or partially for willfully causing loss, destruction of property etc.

Display of Notice Rule -4

On conspicuous place at the main entrance in English language or the language understood by majority of employees of the factory, etc.

Nomination Sec-6 (Rule -6)

To be obtained by employer after expiry of one year's service, in Form 'F'.

Amount of Gratuity (Sec -7)

- Determine the amount of gratuity and give notice in writing to the person to whom the gratuity is payable and also to the controlling authority specifying the amount of gratuity so determined.
- The employer shall arrange to pay the amount of gratuity within 30 days from the date it becomes payable to the person to whom the gratuity is payable.

Recovery of Gratuity [Sec -8 (Rule-8)]

To apply within 30 days in Form I when not paid within 30 days.

Mode of payment Rule -9

Cash or, if so desired, by Bank Draft or Cheque

Penalties

- Imprisonment for 6 months or fine up to Rs.10, 000 for avoiding making payment by making false statement or representation.
- Imprisonment not less than 3 months and up to one year with fine on default in complying with the provisions of Act or Rules.

Protection of Gratuity Sec -13

Can't be attached in execution of any decree.

Payment of Gratuity Act, 1936 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Rule 3(1)	Notice in Form A	On Establishment	Duly made
2	Rule 3(2)	Notice in Form B	On Change	Not applicable.

3	Rule 3(3)	Notice in Form C	On Closure	Not applicable.
4	Rule 4	Display of Notice	Continuous	Display not made
5	Rule 5	Nomination in Form F	Within 90 days of employment	This has been done properly.

Payment of Wages Act, 1936

Object of the Act

To regulate the payment of wages of certain classes of employed persons.

Applicability of Act

- Factory industrial Establishment
- Tramway service or motor transport service engaged in carrying passengers or good or both by road for hire or reward.
- Air transport service Dock, Wharf or Jetty.
- Inland vessel mechanically propelled.
- Mine, quarry or oil-field Plantation.
- Workshop or other establishment etc.

Coverage of Employees

Drawing average wage up to Rs.6500 pm as amended w.e.f. 6.9.05.

Time of payment of wages (Sec.5)

- The wages of every person employed is paid.
- When less than 1000 persons are employed shall be paid before the expiry of the 7th day of the following month.
- When more than 1000 workers, before the expiry of the 10th day of the following month.

Wages to be paid in current coins or currency notes (Sec.6)

- All wages shall be paid in current coins or currency notes or in both.
- After obtaining the authorization, either by Cheque or by crediting the wages in employees banks Account

Deduction made from wages (Sec.7)

Deductions such as, fine, deduction for amenities and services supplied by the employer, advances paid, over payment of wages, loan, granted for house-building or other purposes, income tax payable, in pursuance of the order of the Court, PF contributions, cooperative societies, premium for Life Insurance, contribution to any fund constituted by employer or a trade union, recovery of losses, ESI contributions etc.

Fines as prescribed by (Sec.8)

Not to imposed unless the employer is given an opportunity to show cause to record in the register

Deduction for absence from duties for unauthorized absence (Sec.9)

Absence for whole or any part of the day –

If ten or more persons absent without reasonable cause, deduction of wages up to 8 days.

Deduction for damage or loss (Sec.10)

For default or negligence of an employee resulting into loss. Show cause notice has to be given to the employee.

Deductions for service rendered (Sec.11)

When accommodation amenity or service has been accepted by the employee.

Penalties

OFFENCE	PUNISHMENT
On contravention of S.5 (except sub-sec.4), S.7, S.8 (except Ss.8), S.9, S.10 (except Ss.2) and Secs.11 to 13	Fine not less than Rs.1000, which may extend to Rs.5000? On subsequent conviction fine not less than Rs.5000, may extend to Rs.10,000. On contravention S.4, S.5 (4), S6, S.8 (8), S.10 (2) or S.25 fine not less than Rs.1000. – may extend to Rs.5000. On subsequent On conviction fine not less.
For failing to maintain registers or records; or Willfully refusing or without lawful excuse neglecting to furnish information or return; or Willfully furnishing or causing to be furnished any information or return which he knows to be false or Refusing to answer or willfully giving a false answer to any question necessary for obtaining any information required to be furnished under this Act.	Fine which shall not be less than Rs.1000 but may extend to Rs.5000 – On record conviction fine not less than Rs.5000, may extend to Rs.10,000. For second or subsequent conviction, fine not less than Rs.5000 but may extend to Rs.10,000
Willfully obstructing an Inspector in the discharge of his duties under this Act; or Refusing or willfully neglecting to afford an Inspector any reasonable facility for making any entry, inspection etc. Willfully	Fine not less than Rs.1000 extendableUpto Rs.5000 – On subsequent conviction finenot less than Rs.5000 – may extent to Rs.10,000

refusing to produce on the demand of an inspector any register or other document kept in pursuance of this Act; or preventing any person for appearance etc.	
On conviction for any offence and again guilty of Contravention of same provision. Failing or neglecting to pay wages to any employee	Imprisonment not less than one month extendable up to six months and fine not less than Rs.2000 extendable up to Rs.15000.Additional fine up to Rs.100 for each day.

Payment of Wages Act, 1936 in Godrej Industrial Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 5	Time of Payment of Wages	To be paid by 7th of the following month	Payment of Wages is made in time.
2	Section 8	Notice of acts and omissions	Continuous	No notice or acts of omissions.
3	Section 8	Register of Fines	Continuous	Register is maintained as a Salary Register.
4	Section 10	Register of Deductions	Continuous	Same as above.
5	Section 13-A	Maintenance of Registers	Records to maintained & preserved for 3 years	Duly observed.

Workmen's Compensation Act, 1923

Applicability (Sec.1)

All over India.

Coverage of Workmen (Sec.1 (3))

All workers irrespective of their status or salaries either directly or through contractor or a person recruited to work abroad.

Employer's liability to pay compensation to a workman (Sec.3)

On death or personal injury resulting into total or partial disablement or occupational disease caused to a workman arising out of and during the course of employment.

Amount of compensation (Sec.4)

- Death, Permanent Total Disablement (PTD)
- Permanent Partial Disablement (PPD)
- Temporary Disablement whether Total or Partial.

Compensation in case of Death:-

50% of Monthly Wages X Relevant Factor OR Rs. 80,000/- which ever more.

Compensation in case of PTD:-

60% of Monthly Wages X Relevant Factor OR Rs. 90,000/- whichever is more

NOTE: - In case of Death & PTD, if Monthly Wages is exceed Rs. 4500/- Monthly Wages shall be deemed to be Rs. 4500/-

Compensation in case of PPD:-

60% of MW x Relevant Factors x Loss of Earning Capacity

Compensation in case of TTD or TPD:-

25% of Monthly Wages.

First such payment becomes due on the 16th day after the expiry of waiting period of three days.

Compensation to be paid during the period of disablements of during a period of 5 years which is shorter.

Procedure for calculation

Higher the age – Lower the compensation

- Relevant factor specified in second column of Schedule IV giving slabs depending upon the age of the concerned workman
- Example: In case of death.
 - Wages Rs.3000 PM - Age 23 years
 - Factor as schedule IV Rs.19.95
 - Amount of compensation Rs.329935
 - In case of total disablement Rs.395910.

Wages (Sec.4 Exh.b)

When the monthly wages are more than Rs.4000 per month it will be deemed Rs.4000.

Notice Accident (Sec.10)

As soon as Practicable.

Report of accident Rule 11 Form EE (Sec. 10B)

Report of fatal Accident and Serious Injury within 7 days to the Commissioner (not application when ESI Act applies).

Bar upon contracting out (Sec.14)

Any workman relinquishing his right for personal injury not permissible.

PENALTY (Sec.4A)

In case of default by employer.	50% of the compensation amount + interest to be paid to the workman or his dependents as the case may be.
Deposit of Compensation.	Within one month with the Compensation Commissioner

Workmen's Compensation Act, 1923 in Godrej Industries Ltd

Sr.No	Section/Rule	Compliance Objective	Compliance Required	Remarks
1	Section 16	Returns of injuries and Compensation	As Notified	Not Applicable
2	Section 28	Registration of Compensation Agreement	On Entering	Not Applicable
3	Rule 6	Statement of Disbursement in Form C	As Notified	Not Applicable
4	Rule 11	Report of Fatal Accident in Form EE	On Occurrence	Not Applicable

RESESARCH METHODOLOGY

TITLE

A study on effectiveness of legal compliances for employee development

SUB TITLE

A study on 60 respondents of godrej industries.Ltd to measure effectiveness of legal compliances for employees' development.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY-

The study is about the legal compliance and employee development. The essential part of the study i.e. mainly focuses on the labour legislation including statutory and non-statutory and its relation with employee development. The study will help to improve effectiveness of labour legislation in organization and its effectiveness employee. This study will contribute in developing organization to focus on an employee development. It will explore the more efficiency and effectiveness in employee's development in more perfect manner. It will make attempt to focus on employee life and its influence on employee's life. This study will help in enhance the knowledge of legal compliances and how this facility will help to the employee for there over all development.

Objectives

- To identify employee's development through legal compliances
- To explore the employee's perception towards legal compliances
- To enhance the knowledge of legal compliances in present condition
- To improve organizational capacity through employee development

- To contribute in employee's development
- To know overall development of employee through implementing legal compliances
- To analyze the condition of an employee through the use benefit of legal compliances

LITARATURE REVIEW

The development and establishment of a legal compliance system is one of the most important tasks for a organization in order to secure the soundness and appropriateness of its employee. Therefore, the institution's management is charged with and responsible for taking the initiative in developing and establishing the legal compliance system that covers the organization's entire development by deciding a basic policy on legal compliance and developing an organizational framework, etc..

The prime function of legal compliances is to development of policy and it has some Roles and Responsibilities that is to improve the legal compliance based on a full recognition that full legal Compliance throughout the financial institution is vital for maintaining public confidence in the institution and securing the soundness and appropriateness of the organization's development.

Through our history we know that employee or the labor suffer a lot with the capitalist system but with a strong impact of constitutional power condition of employee developed well and this drastic change was just because of this legal compliances and it has very good influence on employee development. We are rich enough in constitutional provisions which play a major role in employee development and make their life more stable and happy.

IMPORTANCE OF LEGAL AND STATUTORY COMPLIANCE:-

Implementation of Compliance Program

The Compliance Control Division implement specific measures of the Compliance Program in a timely and appropriate manner conduct follow-up verification of the status of progress and achievement and report it to the Board of Directors or equivalent organization to the Board of Directors.

Communication and Collection of Information

From the viewpoint of ensuring the full enforcement of legal compliance throughout the institution, the Compliance Control Division collect, manage, analyze and examine in an integrated manner Compliance-related Information scattered across the institution's divisions and departments and, based on the results of the analysis and examination, take appropriate steps and measures. In particular, the divisions collect information in close coordination with persons in charge of compliance allocated to operation divisions and sales branches, etc

Monitoring of Legal Compliance

The Compliance Control Division monitor the status of legal compliance at operation divisions and sales branches, etc. on an ongoing basis in order to ensure full legal compliance throughout the institution.

For example, the division conduct monitoring by requiring reports in a regular and timely manner or on an as needed basis from persons in charge of compliance with regard to the status of legal compliance at operation divisions and sales branches, etc., or by collecting

information on an ongoing basis and conducting a field survey in a timely manner.

Coordination with Customer Support Manager

The Compliance Control Division appropriately maintains coordination with the Customer Support Manager as required under the Customer Protection Management System and provides advice to help facilitate customer support.

The Compliance Control Division collect information in a prompt and wide-ranging Manner with regard to requests for consultations and complaints from customers⁹ that should be recognized as legitimate complaints or that are likely to develop into legitimate complaints.

With regard to requests for consultations and complaints that involve information concerning violation of Laws, does the Compliance Control Division require and obtain reports from divisions, departments and individuals that hold the relevant information in an appropriate manner analyze and examine the information and provide feedback to the division in charge of processing complaints?

The Compliance Control Division have non-interested parties conduct appropriate and ⁹ See Checklist for Customer Protection Management. Sufficient investigations to identify the cause with regard to requests for consultations and Complaints determined as requiring such action.

Roles of Persons in Charge of Compliance

Persons in charge of compliance keep under unified control Compliance-related information at the divisions and departments to which they are allocated, communicate the information to the Compliance Control Division in a regular and timely manner or on an as needed basis and appropriately engage in efforts to ensure

compliance at the divisions and departments. They perform their functions fully based on the legal knowledge accumulated with regard to their operations.

RESEARCH DESIGN

UNIVERSE

All the managerial level and supervisor employee of godrej industry

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Exploratory research design,

Descriptive research design, Systematic random sampling will be used for collecting data from godrej industry.

SAMPLE

60 employees of godrej industries ltd will be selected for research study.

TOOL OF DATA COLLECTION

Interview schedule

DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data be tabulated and analyzed with the help of master sheet and excel sheet.

EXPECTED RESULT

This study will help to aware about present condition of legal compliances and employee development through its implementing in better way. It will explore the knowledge regarding legal compliances

and its effect on employee's life. It will help to improve better condition and development of employee .it will helpful for organization to improve more efficiency and more perfectionist in implementing it.

OPARETIONAL DEFINITIONS

LEGAL

Legal of HR acquaints management staff with employment laws and regulations -- it does not turn them into experts on labour law. It is designed for the new supervisor and manager, but experienced managers will also find it a useful reference. In the event issues develop in these areas, management should seek qualified, appropriate, professional Human Resource and legal support, advice and counsel.

STATUTARY COMPLIANCE

Statutory means "of or related to statutes," or what we normally call laws or regulations. Compliance just means to comply with or adhere to. So statutory compliance means you are following the laws on a given issue. The term is most often used with organizations, which must follow lots of regulations. When they forget or refuse to follow some of those regulations, they are out of statutory compliance. A company that follows all the rules is in statutory compliance.

Many companies are out of statutory compliance, in part because the cost of following the rule is too high, and/or the consequence is too small to worry about. For example, when you start a new business in most USA cities, you are supposed to go down to the courthouse and file a form stating what business you are now in. If you don't file it, few people will ever notice, and if they do, they usually just tell you to file it now.

TIME LIMIT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The time period of Data collection will be 15th may to 15th June

SHORTCOMINGS

Some of The respondents will not able to give all the answer of questions due to the organizational pressure.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

It's from the beginning of the mankind that man do the work to get some recommendation in one or other form against the work done by him and when it comes to the industrial employees, it becomes must that along with the statutory facilities and other facilities must be provided to them so that along with their basic needs other needs can also be satisfied and they can wok whole heartedly and produce the best and become the assets of any organization.

After 1947, the government of India took positive steps to foster the industrial development in the country; on April 6th 1948 the Government of India adopted the first industrial policy resolution for surrounding the industrial development of the country become smooth because of the five year plan.

Five year Plans

In **the first five year plan** in labour welfare field the emphasis was placed on training of craftsmen & organization of comprehensive employment services. Members of welfare centre have been set up during the planning period with the cooperation of employers, employee & Government.

The state government India provision in **the second five year plan** for running labour welfare centers out of the total provision of Rs. 14.10 crores for labour & labour welfare in the state plant of Rs. 2.5 crores was allotted for labour welfare centre.

In **the third five years plan** a provision of Rs. 27.3 crores had been made by the state government for labour welfare programme out of this Rs. 4.45 crores has been allotted. For labour welfare centre, in

the earlier stage the provision for such welfare facilities was looked upon with varying degrees of suspicions as even hostility. Only recent years there has been change of employers, employees & government much of the change in attitude is attributable to the significant work done by ILO in focusing attention on labour & social problems.

The fourth five years plan provided the next step forwards in attaining aims & objective of India planning. In short the aims of the fourth five years plant were as follows.

- To become self-reliant in the field of agricultural & industrial production
- To make the country self-reliant in the field of production of food gains
- To encourage social & to remove economic equalities
- To solve the serious problems such as unemployment etc.

The fourth plant provided Rs. 37 Crores for labour welfare programs. The financial out lay of the fourth five year plant was Rs. 34.88 out of which Rs. 15.90 to be spent on the public states& private sector respectively.

The fifth five year plan envisaged a total outlay of Rs. 532.41.Cr. out of this and out lay of Rs. 37.250 cr. was for public sector and Rs. 16.161 cr. For private sector, the plan provision for labour welfare was Rs 57 Cr. A lot of effective measures were taken to improve the efficiency and productivity of labours. Effects were made to solve the housing problems of labours.

This sixth five year plan has envisaged a total sector plant outlay of Rs. 97.50 cr. The strategy adopted for sixth plant consists in moving towards strengthening the infrastructures for both agriculture &

industry so as to create increased opportunity for employment, especially in the rural areas and unorganized sector.

The main objective of **the eighth five year plan** is Improvement in the quality of labour, productivity, skills and working conditions and provision of welfare and social security measures, especially of those working in the unorganized sector, are crucial elements of the strategy for quantitative and qualitative enhancement of employment opportunities. The programmes in the sector " Labour and Labour Welfare', therefore, lay emphasis on skill formation and development, strengthening and modernization of employment service, promotion of industrial and mines safety, workers' education, promotion of self-employment, rehabilitation of bonded labour, enforcement of labour laws especially those relating to unorganized labour and women and child labour, promotion of a healthy industrial relations situation and encouragement of workers' participation in management.

The ninth five year plan said one of the major concerns of the Government has been the improvement of labour welfare with increasing productivity and provision of a reasonable level of social security. The planning process attempts to create conditions for improvement in labour productivity and for provision of social security to supplement the operations of the labour market. The resources have been directed through the Plan programmes towards skill formation and development, exchange of information on job opportunities, monitoring of working conditions, creation of industrial harmony through an infrastructure for healthy industrial relations and insurance against disease and unemployment for the workers and their families. The achievements of these desirable objectives in the areas of labour and labour welfare have been determined primarily by the kind of labour market that exists. The situation of surplus labour, coupled with the employment of most of the workers in the unorganized segments of the economy, has given rise to unhealthy social practices like bonded labour, child labour and adverse working

conditions faced by the migrant labour. Within the available resources, a limited effort at handling these problems has been feasible.

The main objective of **the tenth five year plan** is the present infrastructure for improving labour productivity and for ensuring the welfare of workers covers only a very small segment of the labour force. The objective of Tenth Plan will be to increase the coverage of the labour market institutions. The essential condition for this is the provision of gainful employment to the entire labour force.

The labour investigation Committee has quoted the views of Dr. B. R. Seth “the India still of industrialist in barren liquidity rather than a wise investment “However it is noted that some excellent work has been done by some of the enlightened employers.

Still the workers have impression that by providing welfare facilities the employers aim for achieve higher production keep their grip on workers by obliging them.

“Workers perception of the welfare facilities”

In Sayaji Iron, Baroda by Harishchandra K. Vaidya. (1981)

This study was conducted by Mr. H.K. Vaidya on 54 workers of Sayaji Iron Baroda; the sample was selected from the entire department by stratified random sampling.

From the data collected was revealed that majority of the respondent were old i.e. 28 out of 54 respondent. Respondents felt that medical helps is provided only for primary help. The recreational facility was inadequate and majority of them are not using it. Nobody is aware about cultural programme. Regarding the canteen facility 12 respondents out of 54 respondents felt that food which is served in not Nutrition.

The study further revealed that 50 respondents felt that the cold water facility is very poor. The respondents also felt that the interest rate of loan is very high of cooperative society. The respondents also felt that the facility is not adequate.

“A study of welfare facility and its utilization by workers”

In New shorok spinning and weaving Mgf. Co. Ltd. Nadiad by Rajesh D. Vyas. (1984)

This study was conducted on permanent workers from all department by the method of stratified random sampling method Out of 4290 workers a sample of 50 workers was selected. The study revealed that majority of the respondents were educated i.e. 41 respondents upto 12 the standard, 70 % of the respondents were utilizing the medical facility through ESI scheme. 88 % of the respondents felt that the housing facility was inadequate and poor. It was found that 90 % of the respondents were not utilizing recreation facility because of inadequacy the workers i.e. 14 of them were satisfied with financial assistance provided by the management. 98 % respondents said that the food in canteen is nutritious and were provided adequately. The co- operative society seemed to be quite popular among the workers 90 % respondents said that they take advantages of the co –operative society’s activities and schemes.

“Critical evaluation of welfare facilities given to employees”

In SG Pharmaceuticals Ltd. Baroda by Atthwal Amarjit Singh (1987)

From the study it was revealed that 70 % of the respondents were falling in the age group of 31- 50 years. From the sampled data it was

found that 54 respondents have educated up to SSC. it was also found from the study that 96 % of the respondents have been working for more than 20 years, 88 % of the respondents are married and most of the workers have more than two children (66 %) whereas 12 % workers have one child . the study revealed that totally 17 facilities (Statutory and non statutory facilities) were provided to the workers. The study showed that the workers had high level of awareness regarding welfare facilities. The workers as they were more experienced, they were aware regarding educational, canteen, dress, shoes, washing, drinking water, cycle stand, co operative society, aid fund, death fund, sort etc. Besides awareness the study also revealed that the workers utilizing the medical allowance, education, drinking water, canteen etc. The study show that the company did not provided school, hospital, housing facility. The respondent felt that the educational fees are inadequate because it provided for the children during secondary education. The workers were investing more money in primary education. The study further revealed that 60 % of the workers with medical facilities. The workers were not satisfied with education fess and housing facilities. They suggested to increased fees and provided loan for the construction of houses.

“Workers Awareness and utilization of welfare facilities”

In Pararih Colliery, Dhanbad, Bihar by Rajkumar Lal (1988)

The study revealed that 67 % of the respondents were between 20 to 30 years. The study showed that 30 % of the respondents were educated up to primary level. 20 % up to secondary level and remaining were facilities. It was found that 43 % of the respondents were availing housing facilities. 28 % of them were living in rented houses and remaining has their own house. The study showed 75 % of the belong to nuclear family and 25% belong to joint family. This

showed that in the search of job many facilities had to migrate to the place. 72 % of them had good working experience of 11 to 20 years. Majority of the respondents were not satisfied with the educational facilities because there were no proper schools and adult educational centre. Only vocational training was provided to them. Majority of the respondents were happy with recreational facilities as it was provided adequately. The family members were utilizing this facility. Maximum numbers of the respondents said the medical facility were adequate. Majority of the respondents felt that there should be improvement in financial assistance and they felt that the amount of the loan should be increased and should be free of interest. It was found that respondents are not happy with the insurance facilities. Majority of the respondents were not satisfied with the canteen facility because it was too far from the work place and the quality of the food and quantity of food was inadequate. The workers were not satisfied with the small rest room. Majority of them demanded for a good rest room so that they can take lunch and dinner properly in a hygienic place. All the respondents were utilizing the safety appliance as it is a must. It was revealed from the study that all of them were satisfied with safety appliances provided to them.

“A Study of 50 workers of Alembic Chemical Co. Ltd. Baroda”

By Devendra Shinde.

Alembic Chemical works is a public limited Company. It produces life saving basic drugs. There were 3385 employee of which 2165 are the permanent.

The company provides statutory welfare facilities like canteen, dress, shoes, and rest room. He studies facilities in six groups like medical, educational housing, canteen, Drinking water, cycle stand and rest

room. Dress shoes washing co –operative society and other sports, death funds etc.

Majority of workers were under age group of 31 to 50 years. All workers have education up to secondary level. 80 % of the workers has been working for last 10 years and 60 % of the workers have more than two children. 27 % of them workers have identified 7 to 9 facilities out of 17. Non statutory welfare facilities like aid, fund in which workers contribute their fund therefore they do not considered as non statutory welfare facility.

Majority of them have opinion that fees for education, death fund and statutory welfare facility are adequate where as accommodation facility and education facility like school are inadequate because of only two percent have accommodation and workers children not studying in company's school.

At least all workers are satisfied by statutory welfare facility but not satisfied with the school and accommodation facility.

Shobha Mishra and Dr Manju Bhagat (Ph.D. Guide)

As labour welfare is a dynamic concept, changes in its principles activities and the rationale supporting them have not been static. They closely follow the stages of advancement of the industrialized society – from police Theory to Functional Theory. Accordingly principles for successful implementation of labour welfare activities ranges from adequacy of wages to impact on efficiency as well as transformation of personality in nut shell, it is extension of democratic values in an industrialized society.

Theories of Labour welfare Activities have been formulated on the conviction that it is man behind the machine who is responsible for achieving mission of an organization. A person can deliver at his best only when he is satisfied and committed to the cause. To keep the

employees motivated and committed various welfare facilities are provided by the organization not only to the employees but also to their family member too.

The term 'Welfare' expresses many ideas, meanings and connotations, such as the state of well being, health, happiness, prosperity and the development of human resources. It includes both the social and economic aspects of welfare. The social concept of welfare implies the welfare of man, his family and his community. All these three aspects are inter-related and work together. The economic aspect of welfare covers promotion of economic development by increasing production and productivity.

Welfare is also called a relative concept, for it is related to time and space. Changes in it have an impact on the system of welfare as well. As welfare is growing and dynamic, the welfare potential changes, as a result of which its content keeps on varying and has to keep pace with the changing times. Also the characteristics of welfare vary for it depends of a nation in all fields. Its meaning and components, therefore, differ from country to country and from place to place.

The word labour means any productive activity. In a broader sense, therefore the phrase labour welfare means the adoption of measures to promote the physical, social, psychological and general well being of the working population. Welfare work in any industry aims or should aim at improving the working and living conditions of workers and their families.

The concept of labour welfare activities, however, is flexible, elastic and differs from time to time, region to region, industry to industry and country to country, depending upon the value system, level of education, social customs, degree of industrializations and the general standard of the socio-economic development of a people.

It is also related to the political situation in a country. Further it depends upon the kinds of problems with which society is confronted as well as on the structure of the industry. It is molded according to the age group, sex, socio-cultural background, marital status, economic status and educational level of the employees in various industries.

CONCLUSION

India introduced liberal industrial policy which is aimed at stepping up industrial growth promoting modernization and technological up gradation to make industrial competitive in both domestic and global market. In this perspective enterprises have to improve their production and productivity which is possible with the satisfaction of labour.

Even today's scientific development of modern techno- production methods higher productivity depends on workers. If they are rightly directed and fully used, it would make a great contribution to the prosperity of the enterprise.

The high rate of labour absenteeism in Indian industries is indicative of the lack of commitment on the part of the workers. This can be reduced to a great extent by provision of good housing, health and family care canteens, educational and training facilities, provision of welfare activities enables the workers to live a richer and more satisfactory life and contributes to the productivity of labour, efficiency of the enterprise and helps in maintaining industrial peace. Hence steps need to be taken on a larger scale to improve the quality of life of the workers.

An Activist AFSCME Local Confronts Welfare Reform

Chang, Tracy F. H.

Tompkins, Douglas E.

Public sector welfare caseworkers confront shifts in U.S. welfare policy internally, facing changes in their own workplaces, and externally, in relation to their clients. This paper looks at an activist AFSCME caseworker local in Chicago to see how it responded to these internal and external challenges. It compares the strategies of two campaigns, in terms of their timelines, goals, educational needs, and strategic concerns, including relationships with other parts of the union. The paper then draws lessons about alliances with other organizations, the need for a program of maximum mobilization, and development of strong and educated secondary leadership.

Measuring Welfare Changes with Nonlinear Budget Constraints in Continuous and Discrete Hours Labour Supply Models

J. Creedy and Guyenne Kalb No 799, Department of Economics - Working Papers Series from the University of Melbourne.

This paper examines the computation of exact welfare measures in the context of labour supply models. It is suggested that the standard method of computing compensating and equivalent variations does not allow sufficiently for the nonlinearity of the budget constraint. An exact method is suggested. The method is applied to contexts in which individuals are allowed to vary their hours continuously and where only a limited number of discrete hours of work are available. Discrete hour's models have in recent years been used in view of the

substantial econometric advantages when estimating the parameters of direct utility functions.

Evaluation of Policy Option to Encourage Welfare to Work

Hielke Buddelmeyer John Freebairn and Guyenne Kalb

Additional contact information

Melbourne Institute Working Paper Series from Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, the University of Melbourne

This paper compares five alternative policy options with the January 2006 tax and social security system. Each option is designed to cost a similar amount of 5 billion dollars to the government at the current level of labour supply. The five options are: reducing the lowest income tax rate, increasing the tax-free threshold, increasing the low income tax offset, decreasing all taper rates on own and partner's income for a number of allowances, and introducing an Earned Income Tax Credit. The criteria for comparison are the labour supply responses, the expected budgetary cost to the government after taking into account labour supply responses, the number of winners and losers from the policy change, the effects on the distribution of effective marginal tax rates, and the effect on the number of jobless households. From the results, it is clear that the option to reduce taper rates is dominated by the other options on all criteria. The other four options each have their advantages and disadvantages; no option scores best on all criteria.

The Role of Labor Education in Transforming a Union toward Organizing Immigrants: A Case Study

This article looks at a series of educational programs on attitudes toward immigrants conducted for the South Florida Regional Council of the Carpenters Union by the author. It details the content and nature of the programs, the key players, the relationships of the programs to change within the union, internal union sensitivities, and the end results. The case is analyzed to indicate key issues surrounding education of this type: its sensitive nature, the centrality of surfacing normally hidden feelings and opinions, the need for decisive backing from key power centers within the union, the blurring of the difference between "education" and "consulting" in this type of labor education, and several necessities/cautions for this type of labor education to work.

Labour in a Textile City: A Study of Workers' Needs and Welfare in Ahmadabad

By: Verma Pramod

Abstract

The basic hypothesis of this study is that welfare expenditure undertaken by various independent agencies does not meet the felt needs of the workers. A socio-economic survey was conducted to identify these needs. The survey covered 356 'chawls' and 43 housing colonies in 7 areas where industrial workers live. The data suggest inter-alia that the immediate needs of the working class are: sanitary facilities, primary school, cooperative housing society, vocational school for children and vocational school for adults. Survey results generally validate the hypothesis of this study. Consequently, two action-oriented suggestions have been made: 1) the managements should, either singly, or in collaboration with trade unions, Municipal Corporation and welfare agencies provide a lead in formulation and execution of welfare projects; and 2) an apex body should be created to coordinate the activities of relevant welfare and funding agencies.

“A Study of Labour Welfare Activities in the Industrial Sector”

In the industrial area of Hisar, Gurgaon and Rewari by Pravin Kumar.

Objective of Study

1. To analyze the profile of the respondents.
2. To analyze the various welfare facilities among the workers.
3. To analyze the satisfaction of these welfare facilities among the workers.
4. To analyze the awareness of various facilities to the workers.

Type of Research

Empirical research relies on experience or observation of researcher with in due regard for systems and theories. It is data based research coming up with conclusion which is capable of being verified by observation or experiment.

Summery and Conclusion

An attempt was made to study the behavior display by the respondents of the organization. The users surveyed include labour, operator, supervisor and mechanic etc. From the survey, it was found that most of the people were satisfied with the facilities given by the company.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the user’s survey.

- Near about 40% respondents are aware about health provision in org.
- 42% respondents are aware of safety provision

- 85% workers say that health facility improves the efficiency of the workers
- More than 80% respondents are telling that housing facility helps in retaining the workers in the organization.
- 74% respondents want that rest and recreation facility should be in industry
- 66% employees disagree that labour welfare facilities helps in reducing the labour turnover
- 62% worker's opinion that labours welfare facilities helps in maintaining better industrial relation.
- Most of people are happy with canteen facility in organization.
- Only average respondents are happy with temperature and ventilation.
- 70% employees are pleased with medical facilities
- Only small proportion of employees is dissatisfied with behavior of supervisor in the organization.

“Manual workers want industrial welfare. Canteens, latrines and masculinity on British building sites 1918-1970”

Journal of Social History, spring, 2002 by Nick Hayes

Twentieth century employer welfarism-that "ragbag" of fringe remunerations and non-money wages

(1)--has, by and large, been judged pejoratively: damned for being a "sugared pill" sufficiently appealing to steal away workers' class

allegiances or so important to them that its threatened denial promoted disciplined workplace conformity.

(2) Perhaps this is to misconstrue the social relationship between employer and employee, welfare and work: arguably a greater balance always existed in paternalistic practices between "coercion" and active "consent".

(3) Critically, however, neither overview sits easily with an alleged, albeit relatively unexplored, worker antipathy to welfarism or indifference to poor working conditions, where primacy was continually afforded to "money wages" and little else. In these terms welfarism, as either a coercive or consensual strategy, was largely misplaced and can best be explained in terms of employers misinterpreting worker priorities.

(4) Yet trade union pressure for welfarism increased through time: indeed, the greater prejudice against giving welfarism a "fair trial" came rather from company directors and managers.

(5) Wrigley notes that when, during the Second World War, joint workplace committees were established in British industry to improve productivity, "as much of as a third of their time was spent on discussing welfare and other matters"

(6) A scenario more suggestive of employer past neglect and worker interest, than coercive imposition. Nor apparently was this simply wartime bonhomie. An analysis of joint consultation foci in the post 1945 period suggests a continuing workplace preoccupation with "tea, towels and toilets".

**Labour Welfare at Western Coalfield Limited (WCL)
project report by Abhishek Kamdi**

Welfare means improving, faring or doing well. It is a comprehensive term, and refers to the physical, mental, moral and emotional well-being of an individual. Further, the term welfare is a relative concept, relative in time and space. It therefore, varies from time to time, region to region and from country to country. Labour welfare is an important aspect in every organization with some added incentives which enable the workers to lead a decent life. There are several agencies involved in the labour welfare work namely the central government, employer's trade union and other social service organization. Welfare services may broadly be classified into two categories:-

1) Intramural

2) Extramural

In order to get the best out of a worker in the matter of production, working condition is required to be improved to large extent. The work place should provide reasonable amenities for the worker's essential need.

Today various medical services like hospital, clinical and dispensary facilities are provided by organizations not only to the employees but also to their family members. Normally welfare and recreational benefits includes canteens, housing, transportation, education etc.

Some large organizations set up welfare organizations with a view to provide all types of welfare facilities at one centre and appointed welfare benefits continuously and effectively to all employees fairly.

W.C.L. Nagpur area has recognized that welfare of employees by improving their quality of life and their family's well being in general will help thrust to the objectives of W.C.L. directly and indirectly thereby increasing and improving production and productivity. This

task is carried on ceaselessly by involving employees, workers, representatives and management representative.

W.C.L. is spending lots of money on the employee welfare. Welfare facilities provided by this organization are unique for all the employees. The only difference is that the top level officers receive some additional facilities along with routine one.

With the help of the project an attempt is made to study the welfare measures provided to employees, what is the procedure, time required for sanctioning welfare facilities and such other basic policies of the organization.

The study is based on the information collected from respondents through questionnaire. The data analyzed is presented in the form of graph and on the basis of that conclusions are made. At last the required suggestions are given.

After analyzing the data it is found that the employees are satisfied with the welfare facilities provided to them by the area office W.C.L.

Labour Welfare in India

By Dr. C.N. Martin, PhD

Lecturer- HOD

Department of Social Work

Shree Chandra Prabhu Jain College

Minjur, Chennai.

Introduction

"During the pre-independence period, industrial relations policy of the British Government was one of *laissez faire* and also of selective intervention. There were hardly any labour welfare schemes. After independence, labour legislations have formed the basis for industrial relations and social security. These legislations have also provided machinery for bipartite and tripartite consultations for settlement of disputes.

Soon after independence, the government at a tripartite conference in December 1947 adopted the industrial truce resolution. Several legislations, including the following, were enacted to maintain industrial peace and harmony: Factories Act, 1948, Employees State Insurance Act, 1948 and Minimum Wages Act, 1948. The payment of bonus act was passed in 1965.

In the early 1990s, the process of economic reforms was set in motion when the government introduced a series of measures to reduce control on industries, particularly large industries. The workers have opposed economic liberalization policy for fear of unemployment while entrepreneurs have welcomed it in the hope of new opportunities to improve Indian industries. The new economic policy has directly affected industrial relations in the country, because the government has to play a dual role, one of protecting the interest of the workers, and second to allow a free interplay of the market forces. Economic reforms, by removing barriers to entry, have created competitive markets. Fiscal stabilization has resulted in drastic reduction in budgetary support to the public sector commercial enterprises while exposing these enterprises to increased competition from private sector.

Labour and Labour Welfare sub-sector consists of six main programmes viz. Labour Administration, Rehabilitation of bonded labour, Assistance to Labour Cooperatives, Craftsmen training

programme, Apprenticeship training programme, Employment Services and Sanjay Gandhi Swavalamban Yojana

Legal compliance and employee development

Labour sector addresses multi-dimensional socio-economic aspects affecting labour welfare, productivity, living standards of labour force and social security. To raise living standards of the work force and achieve higher productivity, skill up gradation through suitable training is of utmost importance. Manpower development to provide adequate labour force of appropriate skills and quality to different sectors is essential for rapid socioeconomic development. Employment generation in all the productive sectors is one of the basic objectives. In this context, efforts are being made for providing the environment for self-employment both in urban and rural areas. During the Ninth Plan period, elimination of undesirable practices such as child labour, bonded labour, and aspects such as ensuring workers' safety and social security, looking after labour welfare and providing of the necessary support measures for sorting out problems relating to employment of both men and women workers in different sectors has received priority attention.

The Central Board of Workers Education through its regional offices is striving to educate the workers to help to avoid wasteful expenditure, adopting cost effectiveness and by enhancing productivity of qualitative nature. They have been conducting the following programmes:

- Rural Awareness Programme.
- Functional Adult Literacy Classes.
- Short-term programmes for the unorganized sector to educate them on their rights, ethics and hygiene.

- Participative Management.
- Orientation Courses for Rural Educators.
- Leadership Development Programme for Rural Workers.

Conclusion and Main Thrust Areas

(i) Modernization of Existing Trades,

(ii) Maximum utilization of Existing Infrastructure,

(iii) Creating facilities for Training of Instructors,

(iv) Creation of Post of Training and Placement Officer to facilitate placement of ITI pass-outs and to promote better interaction with industries.

(v) Implementation of Government decision to established ITIs at each Taluka and promotes women's Participation in C.T.S. training.

(vi) Creation of additional Training facilities in the popular trades under Apprenticeship Act, 1961.

(vii) Creation of INTERNET facilities to develop better MIS.

Labour's welfare reform: Progress to date

By: Donald Hirsch and Jane Miller

The latest Foundations examines JRF studies on welfare reform and related social policy issues before assessing progress made under Labour since 1997.

The report includes a comprehensive overview of Labour's policies. Relevant research on welfare reform, tax credits, the impact of government initiatives, and alternative approaches to reform is also analyzed before a number of recommendations concerning the long-term success of the programme are provided.

Main findings include

Some successes in welfare reform but other issues still need to be addressed;

Progress in tackling key barriers to work such as a shortage of quality childcare;

Poverty rates for people of working age have been falling steadily for families with children since the late 1990s, although they have stayed more stable for single people and childless couples.

The report concludes by advocating a new approach to welfare reform, one which encourages greater emphasis on the quality of people's work experiences rather than simply shifting them into the first available job.

INCREASED IMPETUS TO WORKERS' WELFARE BY LABOUR MINISTRY

The year 2000 saw a number of legislative and executive initiatives by the Labour Ministry for protecting and safeguarding the interests of the working class in general and those who constitute the poor, deprived and disadvantaged sections of the society in particular. The Ministry which is committed to the ethos and culture of tripartism took measures to revitalize it. The biggest initiative in this direction was the holding of the national level apex tripartite conference, the Indian Labour Conference on April 17, 2000 which was addressed by the Prime Minister Shri Atal Behari Vajpayee. The two-day conference attended by the representatives of the Trade Unions, Employees' Organizations and the central and state governments discussed in detail the issue of industrial sickness which has assumed a great significance with economic reforms making necessary redeployment of capital and labour from unproductive to productive uses. In the process of economic re-orientation, the education of workers and

upgrading of their skills has also assumed greater importance and the ILC made several important recommendations to the government on all the these issues.

Industrial tripartite committees

Seven Industrial Tripartite Committees have been revived / reconstituted to look into industry specific problems emanating from economic reforms. Meetings of Sugar and Cotton Textiles have been held during the current year.

REVIEW OF LABOUR LAWS

The Second National Commission on Labour, set up in October 1999 with a two year term, is making a comprehensive review of labour laws to ensure both consistencies of labour laws with general changes taking place in economic policy and also to provide for greater welfare of the workers. The Commission being tripartite in nature invited views from all concerned and simultaneously held consultations in various parts of the country with Central Trade Unions, Employers' Organizations, labour experts, industrial organizations and government and non-government bodies.

Meanwhile, the Ministry held consultations with the social partners to obtain a consensus for enacting new laws or bringing about changes in the existing laws necessitated by the changing economic scenario. The laws that are being amended or have been amended are the Industrial Disputes Act.

WELFARE MEASURES FOR WORKERS IN THE ORGANISED SECTOR INCREASE IN COMPENSATION AMOUNT TO WORKERS

The Workmen's Compensation Act was amended to substantially increase compensation amount to workers in case of death and disability. Depending upon the age and wage of the worker, s/he or

her/his dependents can get the maximum compensation upto Rs. 5.48 lakhs for disability and Rs. 4.56 lakhs for death. The minimum compensation to the workers in case of death has been increased from Rs. 50,000 to Rs.80, 000 /- and in case of permanent disability from Rs. 60,000 to Rs. 90,000 /- . The other salient feature of the amendment is that all workers have been brought within the ambit of the Act irrespective of their nature of employment.

The Trade Union (Amendment) Bill, 2000, introduced in the Rajya Sabha on April 28, 2000 aims at reducing the multiplicity of trade unions by proposing to have 10% or 100 workers engaged in an establishment to form a trade union. At present 7 or more workers can form a trade union.

The Cine Workmen's Welfare Fund (Amendment) Bill, 2000 was introduced in the Lok Sabha in winter session. The amendment will enable the Central Government to prescribe the wages /remuneration of Cine Workers from time to time in accordance with the increase in cost of living. The amendment would also make eligible additional about 33,000 cine workers to welfare schemes like health, social security and education taking their total number to about 63,000.

Minimum Wages and the Welfare of Different Types of Workers in Honduras

T. H. Gindling, Economics Department, University of Maryland, Baltimore County Katherine Terrell, Ross School of Business and Ford School of Public Policy University of Michigan September 2006

Findings

Impact on Wage and Employment for All Workers in Each of the Four Sectors

Presents estimates of the wage and employment effects using the industry, firm level panel data sets. We present both the "simple" fixed effects estimates and the Arellano and Bond (1991) estimates.

The fixed effects estimates of the wage effect in Panel A suggest that higher minimum wages increase wages in the large firm covered sector and in the public sector, while higher minimum wages lower wages in the small firm covered sector. Specifically, the fixed effects estimates suggest that an increase of 10% in minimum wages would increase wages in the large firm covered sector by 2.12% and in the public sector by 3.74%. At the same time, these estimates suggest that an increase in legal minimum wages of 10% would decrease average wages in small covered sector by 0.2%. The fixed effect estimates find no significant effect of minimum wages on the wages of self employed workers.

Endogenously exists because minimum wages may be changed based on the demand and supply conditions in a particular industry, which will also affect actual wages in the same way. This endogenously creates spurious positive correlation between average wages and minimum wages. Therefore, correcting for this endogenously should lower the value of the coefficient on the minimum wage variable. As expected, when we use the Arellano-Bond estimates, the coefficients on the minimum wage variable (in Panel A) fall. The Arellano-Bond estimates suggest that higher minimum wages increase wages in the large firm covered sector, decrease wages in the small firm covered sector, and have no impact on wages in the public or self-employed sectors. Specifically, the Arellano-Bond estimates suggest that a 10% increase in legal minimum wages will increase average wages in the

large firm covered sector by 2.08% and reduce wages in the small firm covered sector by 1.90%. Unlike in the fixed effects estimates, the Arellano-Bond estimates suggest that minimum wages do not have a significant effect on average wages on the two uncovered sectors: the public sector and the self-employed.

In the competitive model, higher legal minimum wages in the covered sector will cause employers to reduce employment in that sector. The workers who lose their jobs in the covered (large firm salaried workers) sector may become unemployed, may leave the labor force, or may move into one of the uncovered sectors. If those workers enter one of the uncovered sectors, then the increase in supply may reduce average wages in that sector. Given that we found that higher minimum wages are correlated with lower wages in the small covered sector, we suspect that higher minimum wages may be pushing workers into that sector. In addition to the small firm covered sector, the self-employed sector and the public sector, we also estimate the impact of higher minimum wages on the number of unpaid family workers and unemployed (who has worked before).

Title of the study “A study of Employees’ Satisfaction Regarding Statutory and Non Statutory Labour Welfare Facilities”. (A study of 60 employees working in Shree Khedut Sahakari Khand Udyog Mandli ltd. Bardoli.)

Objectives of the study

Main Objective

The main objective is to study the satisfaction of the employees in both Statutory and Non Statutory labour welfare facilities provided by the organization for the wellbeing and betterment of the employees.

Specific Objectives

- To study the awareness of the workers towards statutory and non-statutory facilities provided by the organization.
- To know about up to what extent these facilities are utilized by the organization.
- To know how much the employees are satisfied with these welfare facilities.
- To know the opinions of the workers towards statutory and non-statutory welfare facilities.

Major finding was.

Canteen Facility

Majority of the respondents 85.00 % were satisfied with the price of the food item. Majority of the respondents 66.66% were Highly Satisfied with Canteen Facility. Majority of the respondents 65.00% said that adequate and clean urinals and sanitary facility is provided. Majority of the respondents 40.00% were Satisfied with the sanitary facility.

Safety Provision

Majority of the respondents 83.33% said that the safety equipments give better protection. Majority of the respondents 56.66% were Satisfied with the Safety provision.

Medical Facility

Majority of the respondents 75.00% felt that the company takes care of their family's medical needs. Majority of the respondents 50.00% were Highly Satisfied with the medical facility.

Transportation Facility

Majority of the respondents 55.00% said transportation facility is required.

Co-operative society and co-operative credit society

Majority of the respondents 71.66% were Highly Satisfied with Co-operative society and co-operative credit society. Majority of the respondents 71.66% of the respondents were provided loan in crises.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH SETTING

Overview

Godrej was established in 1897 and has since graven into a US\$ 1.875 billion conglomerate with workforce of 18,000. Inseparable from daily life in India, the Godrej name has been built on a spirit of innovation that has made it one of the country's most remarkable industrial corporations.

The Godrej Label has come to mean different things to different people across the length and breadth of India. Companies operating under the group umbrella are involved in a wide range of business from locks and safes to typewriters and word processors, from engineering workstations to cosmetics and detergents, from edible oils and chemicals to agro products.

The corporation had its beginning in India's freedom Struggle. Its founder, **Ardeshir Goderj**, was staunch nationalist and believed that the country's economic be gradation was even worse than its political subjugation and that freedom could not be won unless it become self-reliant. Beginning with Security Equipment & Soaps, the group diversified in to wide consumer goods and services, all constructed on the strength of the Godrej brand.

In additional to building the corporation, each generation of the Godrej family has been deeply committed to worker welfare, human department and environmental meters. The Godrej Garden Township for workers in Mumbai is but one of several community initiatives admiration at home and abroad. Every year the pirojsha Godrej foundation dedicates funds to promote education, housing, social

causes, population management and relief in times of natural calamities.

The Godrej Story is not limited to industrial excellence and enlightened concerns. It is also a human chronicle of determine men and women gifted with vision and uncommon talents, who built a powerful and unique business.

History

The Company celebrated its centenary in 1997. In 1897 a young man named Ardeshir Godrej gave up law and turned to lock-making. Ardeshir went on to make safes and security equipment of the highest order, and then stunned the world by creating toilet soap from vegetables oil. His brother Pirojsha Godrej carried Ardeshir's dream forward, leading Godrej towards becoming a vibrant, multi-business enterprise. Pirojsha laid the foundation for the sprawling industrial garden township (ISO 14001-certified) now called Pirojshanagar in the suburbs of Mumbai. Godrej touches the lives of millions of the Indians every day. To them, it is a symbol of enduring ideals in a changing world.

Background of Godrej Group

The Company celebrated its centenary in 1997. In 1897 a young man named Ardeshir Godrej gave up law and turned to lock making. Ardeshir went on to make safes and security equipment of the highest order and then stunned the world by creating toilet soap from vegetable oil. His brother Pirojsha Godrej carried Ardeshir's dream forward, leading Godrej towards becoming a vibrant, multi-business enterprise. Pirojsha laid the foundation for the sprawling industrial garden township now called Pirojshanagar in the suburbs of Mumbai. Godrej touches the lives of millions of Indians every day. To them, it is a symbol of enduring ideals in a changing world.

Godrej Malaysia, Godrej Singapore and Godrej Vietnam are closely held constituents of the Godrej group, a conglomeration established and operative for over one hundred years with extensive international ramifications and connections. The group has a total consolidated turnover of US\$875 million.

Godrej Malaysia, Singapore and Vietnam are companies that are export oriented and derive a preponderant portion of their revenue from the export of their product range of steel office equipment. Godrej Malaysia, Singapore and Vietnam have been in existence for nearly 30 years and have been exporting to the following countries:

- A) Australia and New Zealand
- B) Papua New Guinea
- C) Fiji
- D) Male and Mauritius
- E) Oman, Bahrain, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Qatar, UAE
- F) Tanzania
- G) Sweden

These companies have developed a reputation in the quality of their product range, the facility of their product assembly, the adequacy of their service and the proven satisfaction of the end user.

Group Asset in India

Combined Sales – Subsidiaries and Affiliates	The Company is one of the largest privately held industrial corporations in India. The combined Sales (including Excise Duty) of the Company, its subsidiaries and affiliates, during the Fiscal Year ended March 31, 2002, amounted to about Rs. 38,400 million (US\$ 790 million).
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Branches (Sales & Services) and Showrooms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · MUMBAI, Ahmadabad, Bhopal, Jabalpur, Pune, Surat, Bharuch · NEW DELHI, Chandigarh, Faridabad, Ghaziabad, Jaipur, Lucknow · CHENNAI, Bangalore, Coimbatore, Hyderabad, Kochi, Trivandrum, Visakhapatnam, KOLKATA, Bhubaneswar, Guwahati, Jamshedpur, Patna
Number of Wholesale Dealers	Over 1,000
Number of Retail Outlets	Over 5,000
Number of Employees	7100 (including 1,200 in sales and service)

Businesses

The Godrej Group has the following businesses (with respective ISO certifications), which manufacture and / or market a wide range of consumer durables and industrial products:

Office Furniture (ISO 9001 / 14001): Office Furniture, Seating and Desking Systems, Computer Furniture and Open Plan Office Systems.

Storwel® (Home and Office Storage) (ISO 9001 / 14001): Office and Home Storwels®, Sofas and Recliners, Home Furniture, Filing Cabinets and Filing Systems, Book Stacks and Cases, Sliding / Tambour Door Units, Personal / Industrial Lockers, Customized Storage Systems.

Locks (ISO 9001): Locks, Door Latches & Door Accessories.

Security Equipment (ISO 9001 / 14001): Safes, Strong Room Doors, Safe Deposit Lockers, Cash Boxes and Coffers, Data Safes, Fire Resisting Safes, Record and Filing Cabinets, Electronic Coffers, Fire / Security Doors, Fire and Burglar Alarm Systems, Cash Counting Machines, Video Door Phones, CCTV System, Access Control Systems.

Storage Solutions (ISO 9001 / 14001): Multiflex and Heavy Duty Storage Systems, Tool Storage Cabinets, Gravity-flow, Mobile and Drive-in System Components, Mezzanine Floors, Cantilever Storage Systems, Workshop Equipment and Special Solutions.

Steel Processing (ISO 9002 / 14001): Roll formed slides for Furniture, and Steel Processing.

Prima Communication Solutions (ISO 9001 / 14001): Slide Overhead and Multimedia Projectors, Teleconferencing Equipment, Fax Machines, Photocopiers, Multi-function Office Equipment, PRIMA Manual Typewriters (available in over thirty languages).

Industrial Products (ISO 9001 / 14001): Precision Tooling's (Press Tools / Plastic Injection Moulds / Vacuum Forming Moulds / Pressure Die-Casting Dies), Special Purpose Machines, High Precision Components for Engineering and allied industries, Sheet Metal Working Machines – Sales and Service.

Process Equipment(ISO 9001,ASME 'U', 'U2','S' & 'R' stamps): Pressure Vessels including Crystallizers, Towers - Distillation, Fractionating and Adsorption, Reactors and Agitators, Heat Exchangers - Shell and Tubes, Tower Internals and Trays, Custom-built Fabrications.

Material Handling Equipment (ISO 9001 / 14001): Forklift Trucks (Diesel, Electric and LPG) and Attachments, Container Handling Trucks, Warehousing Equipment, Spares and Service for Material Handling / Warehousing Equipment.

Construction & Envirotech Services (ISO 9001 / 14001): Ready Mix Concrete, Commercial Construction Projects, Property Development, Horticulture and Envirotech Services.

Electrical & Electronics Services (ISO 9001 / 14001): Electrical Power Distribution System, Energy Conservation, Compressed Air Control System, Central Air Conditioning Plants (Service, Maintenance and Electronic Controls), Electronic Technology Solution Provider (Hardware, Software, Retrofitting, Process Control and Instrumentation, Industrial Automation).

Time Line

1897 – Godrej & Boyce Mfg. Co. Ltd established

1918 – Godrej Soaps Limited incorporated.

1961 – Godrej Started Manufacturing Forklift Trucks in India.

1971 –GIL began as an Animal Feeds division of godrej Soaps

1974 - Veg oils division in Wadala, Mumbai acquired.

1990 – Godrej Properties Limited, another subsidiary, established

1991 - Foods business started.

1991 – Godrej Agrovet Limited incorporated.

1994 – Transelektra Domestic Products acquired.

1995 – Transelektra forged a strategic alliance with Sara Lee USA.

1999 – Transelektra renamed Godrej Sara Lee Limited

2001 – Godrej consumer a product was formed as a result of a demerger of Godrej soaps ltd. Godrej Soaps renamed GIL.

2002 – Godrej tea limited setup.

2003 – Entered the BPO solution and service space with Godrej Global Solution limited.

2004 – Godrej hicare limited setup to provide a safe healthy environment to customer by providing professional pest management service.

2006 – Food business was merged with Godrej Tea & Godrej Tea renamed Godrej Beverages & Foods limited.

2007 – Godrej Beverages & Foods limited formed a JV with the Hershey company of north America & the company was renamed Godrej Hershey Foods & Beverages limited.

2008 – Godrej relaunched itself with new colorful logo & fresh identity music.

Detailed about Godrej Industries Limited

Godrej Industries Limited is India's leading manufacturer of oleo chemicals & makes more than hundred chemicals for use in over two dozen industries. It also operates business in medical diagnostics and real estate.

GIL is a member of the Godrej group, which was established in 1897 and has since grown into a US\$1.875 billion conglomerate with a workforce of 18,000. The company's business was originally part of Godrej soaps limited, which had a consumer products division. That division was emerged, and Godrej soaps limited renamed as Godrej Industries Limited, on 1st April, 2001. This led to the formation of two separate corporate entities:

Godrej Consumer Product

Godrej Industries Limited has three divisions – the chemical, the food division, and the medical division. Besides its three businesses, Godrej Industries also runs four divisions — Corporate Finance, Corporate HR, Corporate Audit and Assurance and Research and Development — which operate on behalf of the entire Godrej Group.

The Chemicals division of Godrej Industries Ltd. is a leading manufacturer of oleo chemicals like fatty acids, glycerin, and fatty alcohols, and surfactants like alpha olefin Sulphonate. The chemicals division has a strong distribution network in India and abroad and it caters to a wide range of industries, among them detergents, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and plastics. The division has a strong and committed management, and its continuous effort to enhance customer satisfaction levels has resulted in it undertaking a comprehensive e-CRM initiative.

The Food division of Godrej Industries Limited is leading manufacturer and marketer of processed foods and oils. It makes wide range of cooking oils, such as refined sunflower oil; micro-filter groundnut oil refined palmolein and vanaspati and refined blended oil. The company also produces a range of fruit beverages, under the jumpin and Xsbrand names, as well as Godrej tomato purees. The division has two factories; at Wadala in Mumbai and at Mandideep near Bhopal.

The Medical division of Godrej Industries Limited was established in 1992 and used to be known as the biotechnology division. It is in the business of distributing equipment and consumable to the medical community. The medical diagnostic division has tie-ups with Becton Dickinson (USA).

GIL has built a strong manufacturing base capable of delivering international quality product at competitive price. It operates two parts, one at Valia in Gujarat and second Vikhroli in the suburban Mumbai. The company's products are exported to 40 countries in north & South America, Asia, Europe, Australia, & Africa and it leads the India's market in production of fatty acid, fatty alcohol & AOS. (Alpha Olefin Sulphonate).

Godrej Industries has a modern, integrated factory at Valia in the Indian state of Gujarat where vegetable oils are converted into fatty acids, glycerin, fatty alcohols, alpha olefins and alpha olefin sulphonates. The plant has an installed capacity of 30,000 tones per annum for making natural fatty alcohols from Feedstock such as palm stearine and palm kernel oil, both renewable vegetable-based raw materials.

Godrej Industries Limited, Valia which formally used to be known as Gujarat Godrej Innovative Chemicals Limited (GGICL) was, incorporated in the year 1989 In the year 1994 Godrej Soap Ltd. (GSL) was merged with GGICL and named

Godrej Soap Ltd valia. In the year 2001 the chemical business of godrej soaps ltd valia was merged and named as Godrej Industries Limited (GIL). The plant started its operation in 1990. The plant is controlled with Tata Honeywell TDS 3000 distributed controlled system lyric, Germany designs. The plant based on its fatty acid hydrogen process and engineered by Davy power India limited.

At GIL valia, vegetable oils are converted in to fatty alcohols and glycerin. Varieties of fatty alcohols are exported to the industry and for industrial application around the world. The grades of fatty alcohols manufactured include lauryl alcohol, stearyl alcohol and biphenyl alcohol. There are exported through agents to U.S., European, Asian,

Australian and African countries. The Valia plant is ISO 9001-14001 certified.

Products from the plant are exported to North and South America, Asia, Europe, Australia and Africa. The Valia plant has a workforce of 350 people. It is ISO 9002 certified and has been Kosher certified for manufacturing fatty alcohols and glycerin.

Vision & Mission

The Godrej vision reflects the collective goal of the company. It was drafted through a large scale interactive process which engaged at every level, worldwide.

When we said we'll build an empire, we also meant we'll build an empire where values such as integrity trust and respect would be the corner stone's. And when you build an empire on such values, there is little doubt that you'll go wrong. So it should hardly come as a surprise that we are an integral part of millions of people's lives, enriching it in more ways than they can imagine. Today, for most people we are the shining example of enduring ideals in a changing world.

Corporate Profile

INCORPORATION

Established in 1897, the Company was incorporated with limited on March 3, 1932, under the Indian Companies Act, 1913.

SALES-SUBSIDIARIES AND AFFILIATES

The Company is one of the largest privately-held diversified industrial corporations in India. The Sales (Including Excise Duty) of the Company, its subsidiaries and During the Fiscal Year ended March 31, 2008, were about Rs. 90,000 million (US\$ 1,900 million).

BOARD OF DIRECTOR

Chairman & Managing Director	J. N. Godrej
Other Executive Directors	. D. Lam, K. A. Palia, V. M. Crishna, A.G.Verma
Non-executive Directors	Petigara, B. A. Hathikhanavala, F. P. Sarkara.P. P. Shah, A. Ramachandran A. B. Godrej, N. B. Godrej

EMPLOYEE

10,200 (including 2,000 in Sales and Service)

BANKERS

Central Bank of India, Union Bank of India, Citibank N.A., ICICI Bank Ltd., State Bank of Patiala, and Axis Bank Ltd.

SALES (UNCONSOLIDATED)

Sales including Excise Duty (Fiscal Year 2007-2008) Rs. 37,556 million (US\$ 780 million).

Milestones since inception

- Godrej group has won international PI audit sustained performance and received prestigious awards.
- GIL valia is the first in India to manufacture alcohol from fatty acid.
- Godrej has received several awards from WWF.
- Nisarga Mitra Award from rotary.
- Man of the tree award.
- Lok shree award for social commitment.
- India Gandhi paryavaran praskar of the government of India.
- President K.P.Narayan released a postage sample.
- In 1995, TQM (Total Quality Maintenance) was launched.
- In 2003 GIL valia is awarded ISO14001 certificate. This certificate is given for the better environment.
- Kalzen technology was launched in 1993.
- TPM (Total Productivity Maintenance) was launched in 2000.
- The company was awarded best quality circle award of QCFF in oct-2000.
- In 1996 GIL valia awarded ISO (International Standard Organization) -9002 certificate.

Investment in plant & machinery

- Investment in plant & machinery : Rs. 182, 28, 76, 715
- Written down value : Rs. 93, 41, 05, 667
- Investment in setting up new EOU plant : Gross amount=Rs. 55, 34, 31, 83 Net amount= Rs. 55, 30, 49, 778
- Investment in domestic tariff area : Gross amount= Rs. 2, 25, 33, 43, 322 Net amount= Rs. 96, 84, 59, 765

Future expansion plan

The year ahead seems to be very interesting and challenging. The world economy curve is on upward moving and hence the outlook for the various product categories of the chemicals division remains positive.

- The expansions of international markets-coupled with tightness in the supply position of some of the finished product predict well for the business and also open up opportunity for growth in position of markets.
- Retaining competitiveness in sourcing is major challenging in the coming year.
- Enhancement of production capacities & improve its supply chain management. EOU being set up at valia would enable enhancement of production capacity.
- Focus on adding value to some of company's by-product, in order to get niche position in the market.
- Collaborative research along with a customer value addition to develop a new chemical for the paper industry.
- Customization of raw material and manufacturing process to suit the needs of a single high volume customer.

Present man power status

Manpower is divided in to two parts:

- Management staff
- Non-management staff

Classification of management staff:

- Vice president
- Deputy general manager
- Assistant manager & executive

Classification of non management staff:

- S1= senior assistant/senior operator/senior technician
- S2= assistant/plant operator/technician
- S3= junior assistant/junior plant operator/junior technician
- W1= skilled workman
- W2= unskilled workman
- W3= trainee operator/chemist/workman

Manpower status as on June 1, 2012

Category	Number of employees
Management staff	106
Non management staff	321
Total	427

Types of communication channel

Communication is a core of information in GIL following are the major channels of communication

- **Vertical channel:**

Vertical channel of communication in GIL is used to pass instruction orders and message from both top to bottom and bottom to top level. Thus both upward & downward channels are active.

- **Horizontal channel:**

Horizontal channel is used to pass the information at the same level.

Modes of communication used

- Meetings
- Internet (mail)
- Telephone
- Circulars

GIL follows open door policy for communication i.e. employees are free to present their views suggestions and queries before superior.

Overall organizational culture

Organization is a group of individual coming to gather with a view to fulfillment of common objectives of organization. All employees of Godrej group share common values.

GIL believes that excellence is not produced by machines but by people. Employee grievance is zero here at GIL. It is an achievement of the company. Organization is continuously working on improvement of human skills and empowerment of employees.

The organizations framework is designed in such a way that it can train people quickly and effectively. It helps to empower them to take bold and independent decisions.

Strategies for the future growth,

Development AND

Benchmarking

1. Strategic planning to develop new product
2. Value addition in the product
3. Forward integration i.e. going a step more value for the finished goods
4. Up gradation of skill of the employee
5. The benchmarking of the company includes getting a notable place in the world market.

Environmental Awareness

In its pollution control measures alone, GIL has invested too much finance. Effluent water treatment involving latest technology is employed to bring all effluents to Pollution Control Board Standards. Even the treated effluent water is being put to productive use in demonstrations farming. Company has always been giving the highest importance in up keeping environment and ecology. The pollution control has been top in its agenda. While the company has selected state of the art technologies with pollution control as always been putting all its efforts and making investment for further improving the quality of environment. The Valia factory is spread over *140 acres* of land. The plant area occupies 45 acres and nearly 29 acres is used for developing Agroforestry using treated effluent water from our ETP. Company is constantly taking care of this Agro forestry and inspires the environmental activities.

Social Commitment

The company is constantly aware of its social obligations. The company has adopted a village named Kanerao, in Valia taluka. The company takes care of the development of the village. Company contributes much for the education of the village students, their health, clean and healthy environment and other facilities.

Achievements

- Godrej Group has won international plaudits for sustained performance and received prestigious awards.
- Godrej has received several awards from WWF, Nisarga Mitra Awards from Rotary, Man of the Trees Award, Lok Shree Award for Social Commitment, Indira Gandhi Paryavaran Puraskar of the Government of India. President K R Narayanan released a postage stamp on the occasion of the Godrej Group's century at function at Raj Bhavan.

CHAPTER-IV

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Table shows the age of the respondents

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
21-30	13	22%
31-40	25	42%
41-50	17	28%
51 and above	05	22%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

22% [13] of respondents are from the age group between 21 to 30.

42% [25] of respondents are from the age group between 31 to 40.

28% [17] of respondents are from the age group between 41 to 50.

08% [05] of respondents are from the age group of 51 and above.

Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 42 % (25) of the respondents are belongs to the age group between 31-40 years

2. Table shows the designation of the respondents.

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Executives	7	12%
Officers	11	18%
Assistant	15	25%
Operator	08	13%
Other	19	32%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 12% [7]of respondents are executives
- 18% [11]of respondents are officers
- 25% [15]of respondents are assistants
- 13% [08]of respondents are operators
- 32% [19]of respondents are from other related designation
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 32 %. [19] Of respondents are from other related designation.

3. Table shows the department of the respondents

Department	Frequency	Percentage
Boiler	11	18%
Engineering	14	23%
P&A	5	9%
Production	6	10%
Other	24	40%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 18 % [11] of respondents' belongs to the boiler department.
- 23 % [14] of respondents' belongs to the engineering department.
- 9 % of [5] respondents' belongs to the P&A department.
- 10 % [6] of respondents' belongs to the production department.
- 40 % [24] of respondents' belongs to the other department.

Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 40 % [24] of respondents are from other department.

5. Table shows grade of the respondents.

Grade	Frequency	Percentage
Management	22	37%
S1	7	12%
S2	23	38%
S3	8	8%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 37 % [22] of respondents' belongs to the management grade.
- 12 % [7] of respondents' belongs to the S1 grade.
- 38% [23] of respondents' belongs to the S2 grade.
- 8% [8] of respondents' belongs to the S3 grade.

Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 38%[22] of respondents are from S2 grade.

Note:

- Management level
- S1= senior assistant/senior operator/senior technician
- S2= assistant/plant operator/technician
- S3= junior assistant/junior plant operator/junior technician

5. Table shows awareness of legal compliances among employees.

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	42	70%
No	18	30%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 70 % [42] of respondents' are aware about legal and statutory compliance.
- 30 % [18] of respondents' are not aware about legal and statutory compliance
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed the majority .i.e.70%[42] of respondents are aware about legal compliances

6. Table shows the safety equipments provided by the company

Safety equipment	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	47	78%
No	13	13%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 78 % [47] of respondents' are satisfied with the safety equipments provided by the company.
- 13 % [13] of respondents' are not satisfied with the safety equipments provided by the company.

Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority .i.e.78% [47] of respondents were satisfied with the safety equipments provided by the company

7. Table showing multiple answers of respondents for providing protection equipment for safety

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	53	88%
No	7	12%
Total	60	100%

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gloves	44	19%
Safety shoes	40	17%
Apron	40	17%
Helmet	34	15%
Masks	39	17%
Ear plugs	34	15%
Total	*53[multiple answer]	100%

The above table indicate that

- 88%[53] of respondents get protection equipment for safety
- 12% [07]of respondents not get protection equipment for safety
- 19% [44]of respondents get gloves
- 17% [40]of respondents get safety shoes
- 17% [40]of respondents get apron
- 15% [34]of respondents get helmet
- 17% [39]of respondents get mask
- 15% [34]of respondents get ear plugs.

Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority of respondents i.e. 88% [53] are get protection equipment for safety.

8. Table Shows awareness regarding minimum wages among employees

Minimum wages	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	50	83%
No	6	10%
To some extent	4	7%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 83% [50] of respondents' are aware of minimum wages
- 10 % [6]of respondents' are not aware of minimum wages
- 7 % [4]of respondents' are aware of minimum wages up to some extant
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed the majority i.e.83% [50] of respondents are aware of minimum wages.

9. Table showing that the employee had filled up nomination form under social security act.

Social security act	Frequency	Percentage
Provident fund	60	33%
Gratuity	55	31%
Pension	54	30%
Workman compensation	10	6%
Total	*60[multiple answer]	100%

The above table indicate that

- 33%[60] of respondents are filled up nomination form under provident fund
- 31% [55]of respondents are filled up under gratuity
- 30% [54] of respondents are filled up under pension.
- 06% [10] of respondents were filled up under workman compensation.
- Thus, from the above table it can be said that the majority i.e. 33 %[60] of the respondents are fall under provident fund

10. Table shows that mobile is allowed only to administration department officers in the company

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	53	88%
No	7	12%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 88%[53] of respondents' are feels that mobile is allowed only to administration department officers in the company
- 12 % [07]of respondents' are not feels that mobile is allowed only to administration department officers in the company
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 88% [53] of respondents were feels that mobile is allowed only to administration department officers in the company.

11. Table shows that industrial law seminar have to conduct by the company

Law seminar	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	48	80%
No	12	20%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 80% of respondents' are thinks that industrial law seminar can be conduct by the company
- 20 % of respondents' are not thinks that industrial law seminar can be conduct by the company
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 80% [48] of respondents are thinks that industrial law seminar can be conduct by the company

12. Table shows the satisfaction for boiler plant security.

Satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	45	75%
No	15	25%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 75% of respondents' were satisfied with boiler plant security
- 25 % of respondents' were not satisfied with boiler plant security
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 75% [45] of respondents are satisfied with boiler plant security

13. Table shows that license is required for deploy labour contractor

License	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	41	68%
No	19	32%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 68% of respondents' are thinks that license is required to deploy labour Contractor
- 32% of respondents' are not thinks that license is required to deploy Labour contractor

Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that the majority.i.e.68% [41] of respondents are agreed that license is required to deploy labour contractor

14. Table showing duration of rest interval

Rest interval	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	60	100%
No	00	00%
Total	60	100%
30 minutes	55	92%
40 minutes	3	5%
50 minutes	2	3%
Total	60	100%

- The above table it can be analyzed that
- 100% of respondents were thinks that duration of interval is enough.
- 92% of respondents were thinks that 30 minutes of rest is enough
- 5% of respondents were thinks that 40 minutes of rest is enough.
- 3% of respondents were thinks that 50 minutes of rest is enough.

Thus, from the above interpretation it can be said that the majority of the respondents were thinks that 92 of respondents are agreed with 30 minutes. i.e.92 %.

15. Table shows do they have own locker in company

Locker	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	49	82%
No	1	1%
Not applicable	10	17%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 82% of respondents' have their private locker in the company
- 1% of respondents' do not have their private locker in the company
- 17% respondents on this question is not applicable.

Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority .i.e.82% [49] of respondents have their private locker in the company

17. Table showing do they get extra facility provided to night shift worker?

Facilities	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	46	77%
No	2	3%
Not applicable	12	20%
Total	60	100%

Facilities	Frequency	Percentage
Tea or coffee	60	50%
Reduce hours of work	00	00
Medical allowance	60	50%
Total	*60[multiple answer]	100%

- The above table it can be analyzed that
- 77% [46] of respondents are getting extra facility for night shift.
- 3% [2] of respondents are not getting extra facility for night shift.
- 20% [12] of respondents are not applicable for extra facility.
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be said that the majority of the respondents i.e. 77 %[46] are getting extra facility for night shift .

19. Table shows satisfaction of welfare facility provided by company by employee

Satisfaction of welfare facility	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	44	73%
No	16	27%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 73% [44]of respondents' were satisfied with welfare facility provided by company
- 27%[16] of respondents' were not satisfied with welfare facility provided by company

Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 73% [44] of respondents were satisfied with welfare facilities provided by company.

20. Table showing data for quality of food provided in canteen by company.

Quality of food	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	34	57%
No	26	43%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 57% of respondents' were satisfied with quality of food provided by company
- 43% of respondents' were not satisfied quality of food with provided by company

Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 57% [34]of respondents were satisfied with quality of food provided canteen by company.

21. Table shows data for transportation is safe and adequate provided by company or not?

Transportation	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	37	62%
No	23	38%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 62% of respondents' were agreed that transportation facility is safe and adequate
- 38% of respondents' agreed that transportation facility is safe and adequate
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 62% [37] of respondents were satisfied with transportation provided by company.

22. Table showing satisfaction of employee for medical facility provided by company.

Medical facility	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	38	63%
No	22	37%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 63%[38] of respondents' were satisfied with medical facility provided by company
- 37%[22] of respondents' were not satisfied with medical facility provided by company
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 63% [38] Of respondents are satisfied with medical facility provided by Company.

23. Table shows legal compliances will help employee to get proper facilities?

Legal compliance	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	35	58%
No	25	42%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 58% of respondents' are thinks legal compliances will help employee to get proper facilities
- 42% of respondents' are not legal compliances will help employee to get proper facilities

Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 58% [35] of respondents are thinks legal compliances will help employee to get proper facilities.

24. Table showing legal compliances will help to develop organizational environment.

Orga. development	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	36	60%
No	24	40%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 60%[36] of respondents' were thinks legal compliances will help to develop organizational environment
- 40%[24] of respondents' were think legal compliances will not help to develop organizational
- Thus, from the above interpretation it can be analyzed that majority i.e. 60% [36] of respondents were thinks legal compliances will help to develop organizational environment.

25. Table showing the existing condition of legal compliance is well as prescribed in constitution.

Present condition	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	37	62%
No	23	38%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 62%[37] of respondents' are thinks the existing condition of legal compliance is well prescribed by constitution
- 38%[23] of respondents' are the existing condition of legal compliance is well prescribed by constitution
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 62% [37] of respondents are thinks the existing condition of legal compliance is well as prescribed by constitution.

26. Table showing legal compliances will help to improve the quality of life of employee

Quality of life	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	33	55%
No	27	45%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 55%[33] of respondents' are thinks legal compliances will help to improve the quality of life of employees
- 45% [27] of respondents' are thinking legal compliances will not help to improve quality of life.
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 55% [33] of respondents were thinks legal compliances will help to improve quality of life.

27. Table showing legal compliances will help to develop socio-economic condition

Socio- economic condition	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	34	57%
No	26	43%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 57%[34] of respondents' were thinks legal compliances will help to develop socio-economic condition
- 43%% [26] of respondents' were not thinking legal compliances will not help to develop socio-economic condition.
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority I.e. 57% [34] of respondents were thinks legal compliances will help to develop socio-economic condition.

28. Table showing legal compliances will need more effectiveness.

Effectiveness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	65%
No	21	35%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 65% [39] of respondents' are thinking legal compliances will need more effectiveness.
- 35% [21] of respondents' are not thinking that legal compliances will need more effectiveness.
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 65% [39] of respondents were thinks legal compliances will need more effectiveness.

29. Table showing that will apprenticeship will help for skill development of employee.

Apprenticeship	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	65%
No	21	35%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 65% [39] of respondents' were thinking that apprenticeship will help for skill development of employee.
- 35%[21] of respondents' were not thinking that apprenticeship will help for skill development of employee
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 65% [39] of respondents are thinking that apprenticeship will help for skill development of employee.

30. Table showing that in company premises cleanliness is sufficient and better for employee health.

Cleanliness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	65%
No	21	35%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 65% [39] of respondents' were thinking that in company premises cleanliness is sufficient and better for employee health.
- 35% [21] of respondents' were not thinking that in company premises cleanliness is sufficient and better for employee health.
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e. 65% [39] of respondents were thinks that in company premises cleanliness is sufficient and enough for better employee health.

31. Table showing the loan facility is provided by company is beneficial for employee.

Loan facility	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	40	67%
No	20	33%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 67% [40] of respondents' were thinking that the loan facility which is provided by company is beneficial for employee.
- 33% [20] of respondents' were not thinking that in the loan facility which is provided by company is beneficial for employee.
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.67% [40] of respondents were thinks that the loan facility which is provided by company is beneficial for employee.

32. Table showing legal compliance will help employee to protect human rights

Human rights	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	65%
No	21	35%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 65%[39] of respondents' were thinking that legal compliance will help employee to protect human rights
- 35% [21] of respondents' were not thinking the legal compliances will help employee to protect human rights.
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.65% [39] of respondents were thinks that the legal compliance will help employee to protect human rights.

33. Table showing awareness of legal compliance among employees is necessary.

Necessity of legal compliances	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	37	62%
No	23	38%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 62% [37] of respondents' were thinking that awareness of legal compliance among employees is necessary.
- 38% [23] of respondents' were not thinking that awareness of legal compliances among employee is necessary.
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.62%[37] of respondents were thinks that the awareness of legal compliances among employees is necessary

34. Table showing the satisfaction of grievance handling mechanism in company.

Grievance handling	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	36	60%
No	24	40%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 60% [36] of respondents' are thinking that grievance handling mechanism is satisfied.
- 40% [24] of respondents' are not thinking that grievance handling mechanism is satisfied.
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority of respondents i.e.60%[36] were thinks that the grievance handling mechanism is satisfied

35. Table showing employee need training regarding legal compliance.

Training	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	41	68%
No	19	32%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 68% [41] of respondents' were thinking that employee need training regarding legal compliance.
- 32% [19] of respondents' were not thinking that employee does not need training regarding legal compliance.
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.68% [41] of respondents were thinks that the employee need training regarding legal compliance.

36. Table showing awareness about labour welfare fund.

Labour welfare fund	Frequency	percentage
Yes	38	63%
No	22	37%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 63%[38] of respondents' are aware about labour welfare fund
- 37%[22] of respondents' are not aware about labour welfare fund
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.63% [38] of respondents are aware about labour welfare fund.

37. Table showing aware employee for legal compliance through different methods

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Training	39	65%
Seminar	15	25%
Group discussion	3	5%
Booklets	3	5%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 65% of respondents' are thinks that they can aware employee through trainings.
- 25% of respondents' are thinks that we can aware employee through seminars
- 5% of respondents' are thinks that we can aware employee through group discussion
- 5% of respondents' are thinks that we can aware employee through providing booklets.
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.65% [39] of respondents were prefer training for legal compliances.

38. Table showing management gives them enough support to work out own problems regarding legal compliance.

Management support	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	44	73%
No	16	27%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 73% [44] of respondents' were thinks that management gives them enough support to work out own problems regarding legal compliance.
- 27% [16] of respondents' thinks management will not give them enough support to work out own problems regarding legal compliance.
- Thus, from the above interpretation, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.73% [44] of respondents were thinks management gives them enough support to work out own problems regarding legal compliance.

39. Table showing existing welfare scheme in the company has enhanced overall performance of the company.

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
To a large extent	41	66%
To some extent	21	34%
Not at all	00	00
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 66% [41] of respondents' are thinks that existing welfare scheme in the company has enhanced overall performance of the company.
- 34% [21] of respondents' thinks that existing welfare scheme in the company does not enhanced overall performance of the company.
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.66% [41] of respondents were thinks that existing welfare scheme in the company has enhanced overall performance of the company.

40. Table showing welfare facility will affect on their work.

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	49	82%
No	11	18%
Total	60	100%

The above table indicates that

- 82%[49] of respondents' were feels that welfare facility will affect on their work
- 37%[11] of respondents' were feels that welfare facility will not affect to their work
- Thus, from the above table, it can be analyzed that the majority i.e.82% [49] of respondents were feels that welfare facility will affect to their work.

Findings

- The majority of the respondents i.e. 42 %.[25] are from the age group of 31 to 40 years
- The majority of respondents i.e. 32%[19] are from other related designation
- The majority of respondents i.e. 40 %[24]are from other department
- That the majority of respondents i.e. 38%[22] are from S2 grade
- The majority of respondent's i.e.70% [42] is aware about legal compliances.
- The majority of respondent's i.e.76% [47] are satisfied with the safety equipments provided by the company.
- That the majority of respondent's i.e.88% [53] are getting protection equipment for safety.
- The majority of respondents are aware of minimum wages.i.e.83%
- The majority of respondents i.e.100%[50] detected 12% of provident fund from their salary,
- The majority of respondents' i.e.100% [60] are detect 12% of PF.
- The majority of the respondents i.e. 33 %[60] are fall under provident fund
- The majority of respondents' i.e.100% [60] has I-card issued by company.
- The majority of respondents i.e.100% [60] are aware about working hour per week [48] hours.
- The majority of respondents' i.e.100% [60] are get overtime payment as per rules Overtime payment.
- The majority of respondents i.e. 88% [53] are feel that mobile is allowed only to administration department officers in the company.
- The majority of respondent's i.e. 80% [48] are thinks that industrial law seminar can be conduct by the company

- The majority of respondents i.e. 75% [45] are satisfied with boiler plant security
- The majority of respondents' i.e.68% [41] are agreed that license is required to deploy contractor labor.
- The majority of respondents are paid with pay for weekly off.
- The majority of the respondents' i.e.92 % [55] are agreed with 30 minutes of interval.
- The majority of respondents' i.e.82% [49] has their private locker in the company.
- the majority of the respondents i.e. 42 %[46]are getting extra facility for night shift
- The majority of respondents are satisfied with welfare facility provided by company. i.e. 73%
- The majority of respondents' i.e. 57% [44] are satisfied with quality of food provided by company.
- The majority of respondents' i.e. 62% [37] are satisfied with transportation provided by company.
- The majority of respondents' i.e. 63% [38] are satisfied with medical facility provided by company.
- The majority of respondents i.e. 58% [35] are think legal compliances will help employee to get proper facilities.
- The majority of respondents i.e. 60% [36] are think legal compliances will help to develop organizational environment.
- The majority of respondents i.e. 55% [33] are think legal compliances will help to improve quality of life.
- The majority of respondents I.e. 57% [34] are thinks legal compliances will help to develop socio-economic condition.
- The majority of respondents i.e. 65% [39] are think legal compliances will need more effectiveness.
- The majority of respondents i.e. 65% [39] are thinking that apprenticeship will help for skill development of employee.

- The majority of respondents i.e. 65% [39] are thinks that in company premises cleanliness is sufficient and enough for better employee health.
- The majority of respondent's i.e.67% [40] are thinks that the loan facility which is provided by company is beneficial for employee.
- The majority of respondents i.e.65%[39] are thinks that the legal compliance will help employee to protect human rights
- The majority of respondents i.e.62%[37]are thinks that the awareness of legal compliances among employees is necessary
- The majority of respondents i.e.60%[36] are thinks that the grievance handling mechanism is satisfied
- The majority of respondents' i.e.68% [41] are thinks that the employee needs training regarding legal compliance.
- The majority of respondents' i.e.63% [38] is aware about labour welfare fund.
- The majority of respondents' i.e.65% [39] are preferring training for legal compliances.
- the majority of respondents i.e.73% [44] are thinks management gives them enough support to work out own problems regarding legal compliance.
- The majority of respondent's i.e.66% [41] are thinks that existing welfare scheme in the company has enhanced overall performance of the company.
- That the majority of respondents i.e.82%. [49] Are feels that welfare facility will affect to their work?

CONCLUSION

In this section conclusion are drawn based on findings.

It can be clearly seen from the respondents' response that, legal compliance imparted is knowledge of labour law, specific policies and guidelines,

It helps employee to get maximum practice of legal compliance and satisfactory implemented in Godrej Industries Ltd. It is also seen that, the opinion of respondents towards the function of the legal compliance was very positive. From this it can be easily concluded that, perception of the respondents is positive.

The adequacy of the all Acts and policies, applicability, effective participation of the all employee has lead to positive impact in organizational environment.

Most of the respondents have good experience .All respondents feel that, adequate importance should be give to the legal compliance, they also feel that, training and information of legal compliance is sufficient and also a necessary . Legal compliance are given due importance in the organization and therefore it is well planned.

Majority of respondents are aware about legal compliance and that's shows that employee have enough awareness regarding different compliances which is necessary for employee.

Here it shows that in GIL employees are equipped with safety equipment and aware about necessary precaution which is provided by organization.

Majority of respondents knows about minimum wages provided to worker in company.

It can be clearly seen from the respondents' response that, they all have I-card issued by company.

It can be clearly seen from the respondents' response that, they all are aware about the provision and working hour per day.

It also been observed that they all are feels that mobile is only allowed to administration department because they have sensitive machine so they cannot use mobile in nearby the plants so 88% of respondents feels this.

From the above number it can be interpret that training of legal compliance is necessary for employee for better growth and knowledge and it will help and enhance their capability with the help of more knowledge and information of legal compliance.

Moreover respondents feel that existing condition of welfare schemes will improve their life standard and also develop organizational performance.

It also has been analyzed that welfare facility has direct impact on their work and if they get good and adequate services than it will improve their productivity and concentrate on work and apart from this develop more sense of secure and discipline

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the finding and conclusion the suggestions are drawn.

- There should be initiate for importance of legal compliance as well as the employee development in the organization.
- There should be providing proper Training so it helps to familiar and outcome the potentiality of the new employees.
- There should be takes interest and spends time for training session for legal compliance Training for maintain meaningful relation between employee and employer.
- There should be clearly need of the organization to know about laws and aware them for better work.
- There should be well defined policies for employee so they can easily understand and can work accordance with laws so it will directly improve the work culture of the organization.
- There should be well-designed and widely shared induction policy in the company.

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ANNEXURE

INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am student of the **MSW** of **N.S.PATEL ARTS COLLEGE ANAND.S.P.UNIVERSITY**, as part of the course I have to prepare research project report. I take the study on “Legal Compliance and Employee Development” of Godrej Industries Limited, Valia. I would be grateful if you kindly co-operate and fill up this questionnaire.

The information provided will surely be used for academic purpose only and would keep confidential.

Personal Details

1. Name of the Employee : _____

2. Age:

- A. 21-30
- B. 31-40
- C. 41-50
- D. 51 and above

3. Designation

- A. Executives
- B. Officers
- C. Assistant
- D. Operator
- E. Other

4. Department :

A. BOILER

B. ENGINEERING

C. P&A

D. PRODUCTION

E. OTHER

5. Grade :

A. Management level

B. S1= senior assistant/senior operator/senior technician

C. S2= assistant/plant operator/technician

D. S3= junior assistant/junior plant operator/junior technician

6) Are you aware of Legal & Statutory Compliance?

A. Yes []

B. No []

7) Are you satisfied with the safety equipments provided by the company?

A. Yes []

B. No []

8) Which of the following protection equipments do you get for safety?

1. Gloves []

2. Safety Shoes []

3. Apron []

4. Helmet []

5. Mask []

6. Ear Plugs []

9) Are you Aware of Minimum Wages?

- A. Yes []
- B. No []
- C. To some extent []

10) How many % of Provident Fund deducted from your salary?

- A. Yes []
- B. No []
- 1. 12%
- 2. 14%
- 3. 10%

11) Have you filled up nomination Form under following Acts?

- A. Provident Fund [] Yes [] No
- B. Gratuity [] Yes [] No
- C. Pension [] Yes [] No
- D. Workmen Compensation [] Yes [] No

12) Do you have I-Card issued by the Company?

- A. Yes []
- B. No []

13) Do you know how many hours you have to work in a Week?

- A. Yes []
- B. No []
- 1. 48
- 2. 42
- 3. 52
- 4. 46

14) Do you get overtime payment as per act?

A. Yes

B. No

15) Do you feel that Mobile is allowed only to Administration Department officer in the Company?

A. Yes

B. No

16) Do you think that Industrial Law Seminar to be Conduct by the company?

A. Yes

B. No

17) Are you satisfied with Boiler Plant Security?

A. Yes

B. No

18) Whether License is required to deploy Contractor Labor?

A. Yes

B. No

19) Whether weekly off allowed with Pay or Without Pay to worker?

A. With Pay

B. Without Pay

20) Do you think that Duration of Rest Interval is enough?

A. Yes []

B. No []

1. 30 mint

2. 40 mint

3. 50 mint

21) Does you have locker provided by the Company?

A. Yes

B. No

C. N.A

22) Is there any extra facilities provided to night shift worker?

A. Yes

B. No

A. Tea or Coffee

B. Reduce hours of work

C. Medical allowance

D. No facility

E. Not Applicable

23) Has any of the following provision been made for the future of Non management Staff?

A. Provident Fund : Yes No

B. Gratuity : Yes No

C. Pension : Yes No

24] Are you satisfied with welfare facility provided to you?

A. Yes

B. No

25) The quality of food is good?

A. Yes

B. No

26) The transportation facility provided is safe and adequate?

A. Yes

B. No

27) are you satisfied with medical facilities provided by company?

A. Yes

B. No

28) Do you think that legal compliances will help employee to get proper facilities?

A. Yes

B. No

29) Do you think that legal compliance will help to develop organizational environment?

A. Yes

B. No

30) Do you think that the existing condition of legal compliances is well as prescribed by constitution?

A. Yes

B. No

31) Do you think that legal compliance will help to improve the quality of life of employee?

A. Yes

B. No

32) Do you think that legal compliance will help to develop economically and socially?

A. Yes

B. No

33) Do you think that legal compliance needs more effectiveness?

A. Yes

B. No

34) Do you think the apprenticeship will help for skill development of employee?

A. Yes

B. No

35) Do you think that here cleanliness is sufficient enough for better employee health?

A. Yes

B. No

36) Do you think that the loan facility which is provided by company is beneficial for employee?

A. Yes

B. No

37) Do you think that legal compliance will help employee to protect human rights?

A. Yes

B. No

38) Do you think that awareness of legal compliance among employee is necessary?

A. Yes

B. No

39) Do you think that grievance handling mechanism is satisfied?

A. Yes

B. No

40) Do you think that employee need training regarding legal compliance?

A. Yes

B. No

41) Are you aware about labour welfare fund?

A. Yes

B. No

42) How Can we aware the employee about legal compliance?

Through,

A. Training

B. Seminar

C. Group discussion

D. Booklet

E. Other

43) Do you think that management gives you enough support to work out your Problems regarding legal compliance?

A. Yes

B. No

44) The existing welfare scheme in the company has enhanced the overall performance of the organization?

A. To a large extent

B. To some extent

C. Not at all

45) If welfare facility are not provided to you than it will affect your work?

A. Yes

B. No